

Best Practice Climate Impact Assessment Procedures for Planning and
Development: A Review Beyond Compliance

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Introduction

The built environment affects all aspects of our lives, from our buildings, transport networks, distribution systems, land-use, and infrastructure – our society relies on this man-made landscape to function (Attia, 2018). It is well documented that human activity is causing increased global warming due to the release of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions which is in turn causing the earth's climate to change (IPCC, 2021). Some of these anthropogenic GHGs derive from many aspects of the built environment such as transportation and infrastructure, materials and construction, operational energy consumption, and land-use change (O'Hegarty and Kinnane, 2022). The built environment is therefore intrinsic to addressing climate change - from reducing emissions to dealing with vulnerabilities caused by climate change impacts, to enabling behavioural change (Hurlimann et al, 2022).

The built environment has a significant role to play in developing solutions that mitigate the causes and effects of climate change and is thus central to climate action planning (Scott et al, 2019). This is evident when reviewing cross-cutting policies such as the Government of Ireland's Climate Action Plan, demonstrating the interaction between socio-economic development and the climate agenda (Chandy, 2023).

Environmental assessment provides a means of predicting and mitigating the environmental impacts associated with the built environment. The UN Environment Programme (UNEP) describes Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) as *'an examination, analysis and assessment of planned activities with a view to ensuring environmentally sound and sustainable development'* (UNEP, 2004). This typically involves expert assessments (covering various environmental and social disciplines), the application of mitigation measures as required, and engagement in public consultation, before a decision is made to determine if a proposed project can proceed, possibly with conditions (EPA, 2022).

EIA procedures are established in Ireland, driven by EU legislation, to ensure that administrative authorities are aware of the environmental impacts likely to result from the projects they approve. The revised EIA Directive (2014/52/EU) includes a requirement that EIA reports *'assess the impact of projects on climate (for example greenhouse gas emissions) and their vulnerability to climate change.'* Over the last number of years Climate Impact Assessment (CIA) has become a

crucial component of EIA whereby many developers utilise the process to implement necessary climate mitigation and adaptation.

Given the inter-relationship between climate change and the built environment, the climate component of EIA has gathered attention exponentially in recent years – which is justified considering that the infrastructural development taking place now will still be operational by 2050. CIA methodologies are relatively novel and are proving challenging, with ambiguity as to what is considered ‘best practice.’ There are an increasing number of climate issues arising at the planning and development stage (Rollits, 2020, O’Riordan, 2022). Climate related appeals are becoming more frequent (Mayer, 2019), exacerbated by the apparent inconsistencies in the interpretation of climate policy targets and variable assessment approaches applied at project level (Ni Aodha, 2022).

Typically, guidance documents are used by EIA practitioners to translate the regulatory expectation into practice (Morrison-Saunders, 2021). Guidance documents provide a potential means of closing the gap between top-down policy and project level implementation. Thus, EIA is the entry point for facilitating sustainable development aligned to policy targets.

Despite the availability of guidance documents, practitioners and developers are still facing significant challenges when undertaking CIA, with more and more issues coming up during the planning and development process related to climate change. To address these challenges this research aims to:

- (i) gain a thorough understanding of the issues, challenges, and weaknesses of current project CIA approaches in Ireland, through industry perspectives;
- (ii) assess if and how the currently available guidance documents, representing ‘best practice,’ address these issues; and
- (iii) make recommendations for improvement of CIA methodologies, which can be incorporated into future guidance documents, targeting an ‘integrated approach’ covering cross-cutting issues and wider implications.

The research will enable an improved understanding of CIA in Ireland and the wider environmental and policy implications, contributing to the enhancement of EIA procedures and providing detailed consideration of matters relating to climate change in planning and development for the built environment. The research applies a cross-cutting lens with practical application a focal point.

Methodology

The research is focused on new projects in the built environment that are subject to the requirements of an EIA under Directive 2014/52/EU. The focus is on Ireland, however, learnings from international practice particularly the UK and EU will be regarded. CIA is considered in detail but as a component of EIA, the wider EIA procedures are also considered. To comply with the requirements of the EIA Directive, CIA includes the assessment of impacts relating to GHG emissions and climate resilience and the incorporation of mitigation and adaptation to reduce adverse impacts.

The research comprises the collection of an evidence base through literature; semi-structured interviews with industry professionals working close to CIA and / or CIA topics; the development of an assessment framework for CIA guidance documents based on the interview findings; and a review of said guidance documents utilising the assessment framework.

Literature

The literature review encompassed a document search based on keywords and terminology associated with ‘Climate Impact Assessment’, ‘Environmental Impact Assessment’, ‘climate change’, ‘decarbonisation,’ ‘adaptation,’ ‘environmental assessment,’ ‘climate policy,’ and ‘the built environment’. The databases that were used included Science Direct, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The studies were selected based on the articulated evidence and the detail provided on current best practice approaches and relevant challenges associated with CIA. There were not many studies based specifically in Ireland, therefore, most of the selected literature was focused on the UK or other European countries, with the same or similar legislative contexts. The studies were primarily within the last 10 years given that recent legislation is driving both EIA and CIA approaches. The selected literature mainly comprised peer-reviewed articles, Government reports, technical reports, working papers and policy.

The purpose of the literature review was to establish an evidence base of the documented challenges and opportunities associated with best practice approaches to CIA which could be applicable in Ireland. This evidence base was then used to inform the subsequent research by helping to identify the current state of play which was used to formulate discussion points for the interviews.

Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were undertaken to gain industry insight from practitioners working mainly in Ireland (and a small number in the UK). This industry perspective provides recent evidence of the challenges and opportunities associated with the practical implementation of CIA which may not have been captured in the literature. Therefore, the interviews were primarily with CIA and EIA practitioners, as well as a small number of developers. Some interviewees also had experience in climate policy, climate in design and the development of guidance / standards relating to CIA.

The interviewees were selected based on relevant expertise in CIA and EIA of projects in the built environment in Ireland and complemented with UK based practitioners. As many of the guidance documents applied in Ireland are also utilised (and often developed) in the UK with much of their climate policy a few steps ahead of Ireland, there was potential to gain further insight which can be applied to the Irish context. A few interviewees were selected to represent specifically the various groups of informants (similar to Jirricka-Purrer et al 2022) namely: (i) CIA expert, (ii) climate policy and strategy expert, (iii) EIA manager, (iv) carbon focused designer, and (v) developer. The interviewees were selected from a total of 9 companies that have expertise in CIA which primarily comprised large, well-established, international engineering consultancies, involved in prominent projects in the built environment, in addition to a small number of developers (covering both public and private sector as well as both infrastructure and property). All interviewees selected have a minimum of 5 years work experience with a certain level of seniority and responsibility within their roles and are currently trying to make a difference in terms of climate action on projects in the built environment.

The approach taken for the semi-structured interviews is similar to the approach taken by Jirricka-Purrer et al (2016) and Kagstrom (2016). A pre-determined set of interview questions was developed, using the evidence base gathered from literature, and, following ethical approval, shared by email with interviewees prior to the interview. Whilst the questions were used to provide some structure, the interview process was left flexible to accommodate and explore emerging areas, allowing interviewees to raise new topics for discussion, relevant to their own experience. The interviews ranged between 30 to 60 minutes.

The interview questions are included in **Appendix A**.

The data collected from the interviews was qualitatively analysed through manual review. This method was chosen to ensure bespoke and thorough review and was suitable given the small size of the data set. An initial high-level review was undertaken to make note of commonalities, discrepancies and inconsistencies between answers including the potential influence of a person's background or experience. Following this, a qualitative thematic analysis was undertaken to categorise the key points from each interview into themes, through a detailed review of the interview responses. This qualitative thematic analysis approach is similar to the keyword groupings approach applied by Hellsten et al (2022).

This thematic categorisation allowed the overlaps and common issues to be revealed. The key points from the thematic analysis were collated and subsequently refined to generate the consensus and contrasting points, with some of the most representative and insightful quotes recorded. The top challenges and opportunities were quantified by measuring the number of occurrences of each challenge and opportunity within the interview responses.

Framework for Appraisal of Guidance Documents

Using the insights gained from the thematic analysis, a framework was developed to appraise the current best practice approaches contained within selected guidance documents for CIA and EIA. The appraisal aims to reveal the strengths, weaknesses, gaps (specifically, any missing or incomplete instructions), and uncertainties associated with CIA approaches and the currently available guidance documents implemented in Ireland.

The guidance documents were selected for review based on a high-level screening exercise focused on their relevance for use in CIA in the Irish context. The screening exercise was informed by literature, interviews, and prior knowledge of the industry. It should be noted that not all guidance documents are publicly available as membership access to some standards bodies is required.¹

The framework uses a simple RAG (red, amber, green) scoring system (Table 1) for various criteria under three headings – (i) challenges, (ii) opportunities, and (iii) effectiveness (Table 2). The top challenges and opportunities identified from the interviews were used to inform the criteria under these headings. The effectiveness criteria were developed to capture the influence, clarity, and usability of the guidance document itself.

¹ Therefore, an accessible reference link cannot be provided for all guidance documents.

Table 1 RAG Score Description

RAG SCORE	Description
Weak	Incorporating very little or none of the described characteristics. Underperforming in terms of practitioners expectations and needs.
Moderate	Incorporating some of the described characteristics. Moderately performing in terms of practitioners expectations and needs.
Strong	Incorporating most or all of described characteristics. Good performance in terms of practitioners expectations and needs.

Table 2 RAG Criteria Description for Assessment Framework

Criteria	Description	RAG
CHALLENGES		
Significance ratings	This criterion refers to guidance for overcoming the challenges associated with significance ratings as depicted in the interviews. This will include instruction on contextualising the impacts, scaling global impacts to project level, and interpreting EIA significance ratings particular to climate.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
Baselines	This criterion refers to guidance for overcoming the challenges associated with baselines as depicted in the interviews. This will include instruction on data gathering and data gaps, life-cycle analysis, stakeholder engagement, and climate scenarios.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
Policy integration	This criterion refers to guidance for overcoming the challenges associated with policy integration as depicted in the interviews. This will include instruction on using policy targets, relating the project and impacts to the policy context, and bottom-up and top-down alignment approaches.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
Mitigation and Adaptation	This criterion refers to guidance for overcoming the challenges associated with mitigation and adaptation as depicted in the interviews. This will include tangible solutions and implementation approaches for emissions reductions and adaptation, clarity on the expected improvements for proposed mitigation measures, and dealing with risk and uncertainty associated with innovation / new technology.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
Cumulative impacts		Weak

Criteria	Description	RAG
	This criterion refers to guidance for overcoming the challenges associated with cumulative impacts as depicted in the interviews. This will include instruction on defining a boundary for cumulative impacts as they relate to climate given the global receptor and localised projects and overcoming challenges associated with policy and multiple similar schemes.	Moderate
		Strong
OPPORTUNITIES		
Design enhancements	This criterion refers to guidance for maximising the potential opportunities associated with design enhancements as depicted in the interviews. This will include instruction on working with designers to incorporate sustainability into the design of the project for the benefit of climate - from proposing tangible design approaches, workflows and engagement practises.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
Early-stage project input	This criterion refers to guidance for maximising the potential opportunities associated with early stage project input as depicted in the interviews. This will include instrucion on early-stage engagement on the project to influence the concept stage for the benefit of climate include tangible solutions and engagement approaches.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
Interdisciplinary engagement	This criterion refers to guidance for maximising the potential opportunities associated with interdisciplinary engagement as depicted in the interviews. This will include engagement approaches from stakeholder engagement with the public, and across multi disciplinary project teams (Contractor, designer etc) and across EIA disiciplines to make improvements across the baord. This may include education or workshopping practises and approaches in terms of project timings.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
EFFECTIVENESS		
Influence	The influnce criterion refers to the impact that can be felt from the implementaiton of the policy. More specifically, it should consider who is taking this on board and what the scale of reach is in addition to the extent to which it can drive change. A more overarching policy may have a broader reach but has lesser specific objectives for particular project types which can be useful for overcoming difficult challenges. There should be a variety of stakeholders involved in its development which	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong

Criteria	Description	RAG
	should translate to the stakeholder engagement processes in the guidance itself.	
Clarity	The clarity of instruction criterion is referring to the quality of the descriptions used to address issues and the approaches provided. The language should be clear and to the point ensuring that the reader understands the instruction. There should be limited scope for interpretation to avoid inconsistencies when utilising the guidance. There should be an easy to follow narrative and the guidance should be be clearly interconnected and communicated as a cohesive document rather than as snippets of instruction that can be piece mealed / extrapolated.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong
Usability	The usability criterion refers to the relevance of the guidance provided in terms of addressing real issues and the inclusion of tangible actions that can easily become solutions that can be put into practice through the assessment and/or mitigation procedures. The guidance should clearly focus on the practicality of implementation. In addition, the guidance document itself should be user friendly and easily navigable for the reader.	Weak
		Moderate
		Strong

The assessment framework approach taken in this research is similar to the approach used by Hurlimann et al (2021) in which the assessment comprised a normative description and a bespoke scale for measuring policies. The assessment includes a RAG score for each criterion, and an overarching RAG score for each of the three headings (“opportunities,” “challenges,” “effectiveness”). These overarching RAG scores for each heading were assigned following a precautionary, conservative approach using the combination of individual RAG scores. The RAG scores for these headings were not combined into a single “overall” RAG score because the assessment criteria for each heading measured entirely different things and are thus not usefully comparable.

The assessment results are then compared to the data collected from the literature review and interviews to gather insight on if and how the current challenges and opportunities are being addressed. Based on this, recommendations are made which can be used to supplement future CIA guidance documents and provide direction for CIA practitioners and developers alike.

A summary of the methodical workflow applied for this research is shown in **Figure 1** below.

Figure 1 Workflow of Research Components

Background Context: Literature Review

To comply with the requirements of the EIA Directive, CIA must include both the assessment of GHG emissions and adaptation to climate change, in addition to introducing mitigation/adaptation measures to reduce potential adverse impacts. There is a need to determine the appropriate application of GHG emissions reductions at project-level whilst adapting to climate change impacts and addressing the wider environmental implications.

A literature review revealed a limited number of research studies available for CIA in general, with most research focused on broader EIA and environmental assessment procedures and regulation. Specifically, there has been scant research within the Irish context and / or with a focus on practical application of CIA within industry. Furthermore, climate change and the associated policy landscape is rapidly changing, and it is crucial that research continues in line with most recent advancements. This research intends to build on the evidence base addressing some of the gaps in the literature relating to the practical application of CIA in Ireland.

Regulatory Expectation

The literature recognises the importance of regulation in terms of influencing EIA procedures. The interpretation of the regulation and thus the expectation for EIA is typically contained within guidance documents, as noted by Morrison-Saunders et al (2021), in addition to compliance requirements and communication by regulators.

In Ireland guidance documents for EIA and CIA have been developed and published by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and Transport Infrastructure Ireland (TII) respectively. The Institute of Environmental Management and Assessment (IEMA) which are UK based but have international reach have also developed several CIA focused guidance documents which are often applied in Ireland given the scarcity of documents developed for the Irish context. The European Commission has also published guidelines relating to both EIA and CIA processes. In addition, there are guidelines contained within EIA project appraisal methodologies and several standards for GHG quantification that may be utilised for CIA quantification methods in Ireland.

Further to EIA and CIA focused guidance documents, the wider policy landscape is influential in contextualising the measured impacts and benchmarking the assessments. This is particularly important for climate, the built environment and thus EIA. For example, Attia (2018) notes clear intersections between building standards such as Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) and EIAs,

whereby EIA can be used to contribute to the implementation of such standards, ultimately reducing the climate impact of new buildings. This paper also highlights the importance of integrating EIA and the various sustainability instruments to achieve better outcomes. Carbon budgets are an important policy instrument in Ireland for reducing GHG emissions, however, the carbon budgets are applied using a top-down approach which can be challenging to integrate into project level CIA and EIA. Priore et al (2022) highlights the need to integrate a bottom-up approach to better assign carbon budgets to project level assets and assess the feasibility of these targets in design and construction realities. As such, it can be challenging to understand the wider policy implications as they relate to CIA.

Legislation requires the assessment of climate impacts as part of Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) procedures for certain plans, policies, and programmes (EPA, 2004). The SEA process is well-positioned to provide coherence (Dzebo et al, 2019) across policies and projects in mitigating cumulative (Gunn and Noble, 2009) climate impacts and thus strengthening the treatment of climate change in planning and development (Posas, 2011). There is potential for SEA to be used to address overarching issues such as climate before it gets to EIA stage thus enabling better policy or regulatory integration to EIA. However, to date SEA in Ireland has not prevented complex issues from arising during project-level CIA in Ireland, with current processes failing to address this gap between top-down target setting and tangible bottom-up solutions.

Whilst regulation is an important influencing factor on CIA procedures for developments in the built environment, it must be acknowledged that considering climate change impacts on new projects is not only obligated through policy but also a physical need. Climate poses significant risk to the built environment which is well documented in literature. Wilby (2007) notes that urban populations and their assets are increasingly exposed to growing risks of extreme weather events, particularly cities and already vulnerable populations. Given that the built environment contributes approximately 37% of GHG emissions in Ireland (O’Hegarty and Kinnane, 2022), it is crucial that new developments, most of which have lifespan of over 60 years, are designed to enable a low carbon, climate resilient future. Scott et al (2019) describes the built environment as an “opportunity space” for creating climate-resilient pathways in Ireland, noting that *“this lifetime, of 50-100 years or more, corresponds to the expected dramatic changes in climate: buildings and infrastructure constructed today are required to both reduce the GHG emissions burden placed*

on current and future generations and simultaneously persist and perform to a high standard in both the current and future climate.”

Climate in EIA procedures

Given the global nature and scale of climate change and the pace of ongoing change, it can be challenging to understand the role that EIA should play in its assessment and mitigation/adaptation at project level. The gap between climate policy and practice can become even more pronounced due to this context variation particularly in EIA procedures. Hellsten et al (2022) highlights that while EIA has the potential to act as a vehicle to achieving national policy objectives and directly targeting sectoral objectives, this is not the case in practice whereby EIA is seldom adjusted based on evolving national objectives. This research also acknowledges that if the scope of EIA were to be extended it could conflict with the interests of a streamlined process which could have negative consequences for development.

Furthermore, it has been found that climate policies are frequently not stringent enough to ensure developments are achieving the best sustainability outcomes which could cause shortcomings if relied upon in EIA. Adric and Al Ghamdi (2018) outlines that national renovation policies of ten European Member States were found to be less than 60% compliant with European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive. An Irish Green Building Council report (2014) highlights the need for Ireland to fully understand the issues and challenges being faced to ensure the necessary environmental standards are in place and in line with European requirements. Recently climate recommendations have become a requirement in annual financial reporting which may result in organisations seeking reduced climate impacts from development regardless of the requirements on the built environment (Cronin and Doyle-Kent, 2022).

In recent years, there is increasing recognition for the need to move away from the “tick-box” view of EIA and reframe EIA as a tool for embedding sustainability principles from the outset (IES, 2023). A recent IES report describes the cultural shift that is needed to ensure that EIA professionals are equipped with skills to meet the challenges of the next 30 years including upskilling and collaboration.

To integrate climate to EIA procedures it needs to be considered holistically as a consolidative part of the EIA, across all steps in the process, as demonstrated in recent research (Mayembe et al, 2023). Mayembe notes that this must include balanced consideration of both mitigation and

adaptation, in addition to cross sectoral regulation and integration with SEA. The varying levels of climate integration across EIA, as depicted by Maymbe et al (2023) are shown in **Figure 2**. This figure highlights the potential ways in which climate may be regarded by practitioners without meaningful integration into EIA procedures and highlight the level of detail required for thorough integration.

Figure 2 Climate Integration to EIA (Maymbe et al, 2023)

There is some available literature which explores the role of EIA in addressing climate change. Sok et al (2011) highlight the arguments stating that formally addressing climate change outside of EIA may remove the need to consider it within the EIA process. However, the authors conclude that considering climate change effects on EIA projects is important from a regulatory and physical risk perspective. Jiricka-Purrer et al (2018) describes how EIA can provide an entry point for the incorporation of climate change impacts and adaptation into project design, approval, and implementation. The results of this research suggest that the framing conditions including the planning system and specific guidance can influence the consideration of climate change adaptation, noting the importance of taking a long-term view on climate impacts. Loomis et al (2022) provides a reminder that ultimately EIA should aim to foster sustainable development, which means that transformational purpose should be inherent in EIA (although it is typically not meeting its potential). Since addressing climate change and its associated impacts is a core goal

for sustainable development (as defined by the UN Sustainable Development Agenda 2030) CIA must harness this transformational purpose.

Challenges

It has been established that the built environment is central to enabling climate mitigation and adaptation. This requires successful planning and development which still caters to the needs of growing populations whilst addressing a future climate (Adric and Al-Ghamdi, 2018). Hurlimann et al (2022) makes the point that built environments are within and part of natural systems and therefore, managing and developing the built environment should follow an inclusive framing. Environmental and climate systems are interwoven with the built environment, with feedback in both directions, and are not mutually exclusive.

CIA should facilitate the right kinds of development aligned to climate objectives; however, this can be difficult to achieve on the ground due to challenges associated with implementation. For example, it must be acknowledged that building and construction practices play an important role in facilitating or hindering the implementation of mitigation and adaptation measures. The Irish Green Building Council (2014) outlines some of the construction practices which aim to embed sustainability within the industry including Green Public Procurement (GPP), the Construction Products Regulation and the Sustainability of Construction Works standard (which provides a structure for Environmental Product Declarations). However, much of the requirements have been voluntary and / or the sustainability requirements have been unclear. Attia (2018) describes selecting low-impact materials as a complex and multifaceted task, requiring input from various disciplines as early in the project as possible.

Another challenge that can hinder successful implementation of climate solutions on projects, is the lack of appropriate resources and knowledge, which can result in a failure to adequately assess and reduce climate impacts. Hurlimann et al (2022) describes that the three major barriers to climate change action relate to funding, knowledge, and time frames, noting the high costs of climate action within the construction sector. Nita et al (2022) notes that the common issues obstructing EIAs proper implementation and include low quality assessments, insufficient equipment or trained staff, and low levels of cooperation or participation.

There is recognition in the literature for the political nature of EIA which can either act to push forward climate objectives through development or act as a blocker. Bond et al (2020) stipulates

that EIA can only make decision-making more accountable if it is depoliticised, referring to studies which argue that the concept of sustainable development is used because it is ambiguous and can be interpreted as desired by political parties. Enriquez-de-Salamanca (2020) describes that EIA can be ineffective at rejecting projects with dubious justification especially when they have political support, noting that project justification should be reinforced in EIA documents. According to Fischer et al (2016), there is some evidence that ambition to carry out best practice in EIA may be declining whereby environmental assessment is seen as a constraint to economic development.

The failure to adequately follow-up is a well-recognised weakness in EIA procedures which thus holds true for CIA as part of the process. Nisbet et al (2022) conducted a study to evaluate the quality of EIA procedures which revealed that monitoring and follow-up is the worst performing aspect of EIAs. Jha-Thakur (2016) notes that the weak monitoring regime associated with EIAs fails to maximise the potential to “learn from experience.” Similarly, Mayembe et al (2023) recommends that Environmental Management Plans should be used for periodic monitoring to update the knowledge concerning environmental changes, climate trends and baselines, again alluding to this “learn by doing” approach. This approach is also recommended by Hochstrasser (2013) whereby a learning by doing principle should be applied when policy is evaluated at implementation stage, putting emphasis on the need for monitoring and evidence-based planning.

Potentially one of the most fundamental issues associated with the implementation of climate mitigation and adaptation on projects in the built environment is the complex, dynamic and multidisciplinary nature of climate action. This is widely featured in literature. For example, Destjerdi et al (2022) and Jiricka-Purrer et al (2018) articulate the breadth of inter-relationships across climate and environmental disciplines in urban planning and Achakulwisut et al (2022) demonstrates the need to move away from a “carbon tunnel vision” and take a holistic approach to climate action. Nita et al (2022) describes this as a “*need to rethink EIA as a collaborative process leading it toward more sustainable, holistic planning by learning from past experiences, best practices and expert opinion.*” Hurlimann et al (2022) emphasizes the need to integrate climate action in the built environment across key sectors including taking an integrated approach to adaptation and mitigation. Jiricka-Purrer et al (2016) highlights the challenge of climate

proofing whilst working under complexity, with connectivity between data gathering approaches as well as policy and planning levels needed.

The need for a collaborative approach to CIA is also highlighted in literature, given the multidisciplinary nature of climate issues. Recent research by Doelle and Majekolagbe (2023), highlights that meaningful public engagement is vital to the effective and just consideration of climate in EIA. The authors conclude that the complex nature of climate change requires a nuanced understanding of and flexible approach to public participation. Innes (1998) articulates the importance of participation and communication with a variety of stakeholders throughout the planning process which she coins as “communicative planning.” Loomis et al (2022) takes this a step further by concluding that EIA should be a tool for deep learning that can transform stakeholder values. Missing a sentence here to conclude your literature and point to the need to identify these challenges in Ireland from the practitioner's perspectives.

Results

Data Collection: Interviews

Participants Overview

A total of 21 interviews were carried out. There were 10 females and 11 males interviewed, with 18 based in Ireland and 3 based in the UK. The 21 interviewees brought different perspectives having all contributed to the planning of new developments whilst trying to drive climate action in varying ways. The % contribution of the different interviewee roles is shown in **Figure 3** below. Whilst these roles are generally their primary job description at present, some interviewees also had different past experiences and / or particular interests such as biodiversity, transport and circular economy for example which allowed them to bring different insights in their answers.

Most of the interviewees currently work or have worked on EIA's in depth however, some roles have had lesser involvement in EIA including the Carbon focused Designers and Climate Policy and Strategy Experts (comprising 28% of the total). Moreover, only the CIA Expert roles have worked on conducting the CIA component of EIA directly (38% of the total), with EIA Managers, Carbon focused Designers and Developers indirectly contributing to the CIA (42% of the total), and Climate Policy and Strategy Experts (14% of total) conducting similar work but at policy and plan level.

It should also be noted that the three UK based interviewees are CIA Experts, with two having contributed to the development of the IEMA guidance document (IEMA (2022) *Assessing Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Evaluating their Significance*).

Figure 3 Interviewees Roles Distribution

Study Design Issue

Whilst there were a total of 9 companies represented by the selected interviewees, it should be noted that the numbers of interviewees from each company was not evenly distributed with one company substantiating a larger relative proportion than the others. However, given the similarities in viewpoints between interviewees from this company and the viewpoints from the other companies, the results are still deemed representative of the industry at large.

General Responses

There was generally good consensus between the responses, though with some outliers and some individual or seldom made points. The consensus for each of the high-level questions is summarised in **Table 3**, including a summary of the outliers, points of contention and insights on the background influence of interviewees that could have motivated different answers. The specific opportunities and challenges that were discussed in the interviews are outlined in more detail in the next section.

Table 3 General Interview Responses

What is your understanding of CIA?

There was a good understanding of CIA amongst interviewees. Many had a grasp on both emissions and resilience, but for several interviewees, their knowledge was stronger on emissions and others stronger on resilience – their answers reflected this accordingly. The most frequently discussed economic sectors

in terms of experience were transport (which can be very significant schemes in terms of climate impacts) and property (both private and public buildings).

There was good recognition from those working within EIA of the legal imperative behind the procedures for example, planning conditions contain the requirement to follow mitigation set out in an EIA (making it a legal obligation). Therefore, there is potential for EIA to be used to drive change on projects.

Do you think that climate mitigation and climate adaptation is being successfully implemented on new projects in the built environment to date?

There was near full consensus on the fact climate action on projects in the built environment is not happening to its full potential. The few ‘lighthouse initiatives’ beginning to happen were recognised but climate action was largely deemed ‘unsatisfactory to date’ in the responses. Several consultants noted that it also depends on the scale, profile and budget of a project whereby large, high-profile projects are more likely to include better climate mitigation measures than smaller projects.

There was recognition for the fact that we are further along in terms of climate mitigation compared to adaptation, whereby, to date mitigation has gotten much more attention in the built environment and in policy requirements. A couple of interviewees proposed the reason for this, is that the impending climate change effects in Ireland are not taken seriously as people do not believe that it will be severe, which may not be the case in other parts of the world – several interviewees noted that we are only beginning to look at flooding (‘learning from past mistakes’).

Do you think that CIA can make a difference in terms of climate action for projects in the built environment?

There was almost consensus on the potential for using CIA to make a difference in terms of driving and facilitating climate action for projects. However, the majority of interviewees also recognised that whilst there is the potential to make a difference, it largely is not happening and depends on things like the nature of the project and the level of effort put into the CIA (‘if it’s done well, it can make a difference’).

There was general recognition for the differences between project / client type and sector. For example, several consultants noted that there is greater scope for innovation in the private sector with much more resistance from the public sector to date. However, it was noted that the public sector is starting to accelerate action now, driven by policy and government requirements.

The ‘de-risking of projects’ was a topic that arose with several interviewees whereby there was a view that developers tend to incorporate climate mitigation for optics and to reduce risks associated with getting through planning and / or to avoid issues with public perception – particularly on ‘risky’ or high profile projects.

When carrying out EIA / CIA is it possible to integrate climate policy targets?

Some conflicting answers were given for this question, whereby some people felt it was quite straight forward to integrate targets, but others felt it was not. This could be due to different interpretations of the question, the challenges associated with top-down versus bottom-up, or inconsistent methodologies and expectations in terms of successful policy integration. For example, some consultants felt that expressing a project’s carbon footprint as a % of a national carbon budget is sufficient and others felt it insufficient. Some specific challenges have been highlighted including issues with incorporating top-down and/or national targets at project level and the impacts to significance ratings.

City level climate action plans were noted by a couple of interviewees as being the intermediary between high level policies and project level action. One developer noted that organisation level decarbonisation plans or strategies could also be the intermediary between high level policies and project level action. Both these points are similar – alluding to the need for a structured, tiered approach to the target setting to enable incorporation to CIA. The intermediary plans have the potential to interpret policies that are context dependent and provide tangible guidance closer to ground level.

Do you think current CIA procedures can be improved?

There was agreement across all responses that CIA procedures can be improved. However, there was variability in how these improvements should be made or prioritised, with one person stating, ‘yes but the question is how?’ which summarises the main point here.

There were differences in the willingness (or not) to criticise the EIA process whereby people who are not directly working in that space (or have moved away from it) tended to more willingly criticise EIA itself, posing the question ‘can EIA really make a difference?’ For example, several practitioners working primarily in EIA noted that you can rely on the EIA process for covering interrelationships and cumulative impacts, but others who were no longer working primarily in EIA deemed these processes as tick box and insufficient.

Is there anything you would like to find out from this research that would help you on projects?

The majority said the research would help their work, but the areas of most interest varied considerably between interviewees. Several consultants mentioned that they would be interested in knowing what

others are doing – how they are undertaking the assessments and what challenges they are having. Mitigation was a topic that came up quite frequently (more frequently than adaptation likely given the policy obligations to meet decarbonisation targets), as well as guidance, policy, and best practice.

Opportunities and Challenges

The opportunities and challenges were discussed in detail, in addition to answering the questions outlined in the previous section. A list of potential opportunities and challenges was provided (based on the literature review and prior industry knowledge) as a prompt for the interviewees, but they were also encouraged to bring up their own ideas that may not have been included in the list. The interviewees were asked to select a top two of both challenges and opportunities. There were 43 top challenges and 40 top opportunities noted in the interview responses, summarised in **Table 4** below. A small number of interviewees provided more than or less than the “top two” requested, resulting in the slightly skewed numbers. It should be noted that the interviewees were more inclined to pick opportunities and challenges included on the prompt list, however, five interviewees (24%) provided challenges that were not listed.

Table 4 Top Opportunities and Challenges

Description	No. Occurrences	% Total
Top Challenges		
Significance ratings – which relates to contextualising the climate impact	10	23%
Baselines – which relates to quantifying the climate impacts on the site without the proposed development	8	19%
Mitigation and adaptation measures – relating to the how, what and when to implement solutions that can reduce emissions and build climate resilience, ultimately reducing adverse climate impacts	7	16%
Cumulative effects – which relates to measuring the combined impacts with other projects but noting that climate impacts are not localised	7	16%
Inter-relationships – with other disciplines across the EIA and design teams	3	7%
Lack of data – relating to the availability of suitable carbon factors and climate projections for the baseline and quantification of impacts (not included on prompt list)	2	5%

Description	No. Occurrences	% Total
Climate action in design – which relates to incorporating emissions and adaptation solutions into the design from the outset	2	5%
Buy-in from stakeholders – which relates to co-operation and support from the necessary actors in terms of the effort required to appropriately measure and reduce climate impacts (not included on prompt list)	1	2%
Lack of guidance – relating to a lack of guidelines available on CIA procedures in general (not included on prompt list)	1	2%
Funding – relating to the frequently low funding provided to undertake the assessment and to introduce mitigation or adaptation (not included on prompt list)	1	2%
Legislative focus – which relates to the legislative procedures that can cloud the scientific assessment process (such as Judicial Reviews and Oral Hearings) (not included on prompt list)	1	2%
Top Opportunities		
Design enhancements – which relates to embedding mitigation and adaptation solutions into the design to target carbon hotspots and vulnerable elements	13	32%
Mitigation and adaptation measures – which relate to introducing new / additional mitigation and adaptation solutions to reduce the climate impacts	8	20%
Scope for influence – relates to the ability to influence a project at its early stages (where most change can be made) through transformative thinking	8	20%
Improvements across the EIA – relating to the engagement and interdisciplinarity with various disciplines and the potential to maximise co-benefits	4	10%
Alignment with policy – which relates to incorporating actions that facilitate national targets at project level	4	10%
Motivation – for developers to implement climate action as it becomes an obligation	3	8%

It should be noted that while the request was to prioritise the top challenges and opportunities, in general the interviewees agreed that most of the listed prompts presented important opportunities and challenges in themselves. However, there were some exceptions whereby a small number of interviewees felt that a particular item on the provided list was not a challenge (due to the procedures developed now or their current knowledge) whereas other people felt that said item was a challenge. For example, baselines, significance ratings, cumulative effects and inter-relationships resulted in this type of conflict in the responses, which may be due to varying knowledge bases, personal experience, or differing interpretations of the question.

Though the challenges and opportunities have been recorded separately, it was acknowledged throughout the interview process that some of the opportunities and challenges are interlinked and / or very similar. For example, design enhancements are interlinked with mitigation. There is also the potential for some challenges to be reframed as opportunities.

There was more variability in the identified challenges including suggestions for new challenges not included on the prompt list (included in **Appendix A**). For the opportunities, most interviewees circled back to mitigation and / or design enhancement and did not suggest additional opportunities. Throughout the discussions, there seemed to be a universal recognition for the importance of influencing the design from the outset if you want to make a difference in terms of reducing climate impacts. This was framed as an opportunity slightly more so than it was framed as a challenge.

Thematic Analysis

The main points and key insights gathered from the interview responses are provided in the subsequent sections, categorised by themes. The key themes identified represent the 10 most commonly occurring topics including the following:

- EIA procedures
- Project dependencies
- Planning versus implementation
- Policy
- Behavioural and systems change
- Guidance

- Baselines
- Mitigation
- Collaboration and engagement
- Uncertainties

These sections aim to cover the individualistic insights that could not be captured under the generalised responses provided previously.

EIA Procedures

There were several insights related to EIA procedures, particularly their suitability to incorporating climate objectives. One interviewee noted that ‘CIA is only one part of EIA which is only one part the planning system’ whereby this hierarchy results in ‘climate not being enough of a focus to be transformational.’ This interviewee recommended that there needs to be an overhaul of the planning system to switch the focus to solving climate change but recognises the challenge in doing so given the legislative context. A developer also noted that ‘the EIAR is often more of a tick the box exercise rather than enabling the embedding of climate action.’

Several interviewees, across different disciplines and roles, described the issues associated with context differentiation between EIA and global climate change. One EIA manager noted that the broader sustainability impacts of the project were not captured in EIA including the benefits whereby only the negative impacts are captured, though noting ‘you need to ensure the data is there to back it up.’ A developer noted that ‘climate change can be quite intangible at project level. It is not the job of the project to solve climate change.’ This developer recommended that if the assessment was switched to a carbon or energy focused assessment instead of ‘climate change’ it might fit better in terms of scale and make it easier to apply significance ratings. Another EIA manager described nicely the challenge associated with significance ratings for CIA stating, ‘significance ratings are different from other environmental disciplines because there is no local context, we are always talking about global significance.’

Another interviewee described inter-relationships between EIA disciplines as very ‘wishy washy’ and much easier to cover from a strategic perspective, noting ‘the inter-relationships are usually just covered off in a tick box exercise which is typically very weak, instead of focusing on maximising co-benefits which could strengthen project outcomes.’

One CIA practitioner described in detail the differences between introducing mitigation within the EIA compared to strategy (SEA) level recommending that ‘for climate action we need to zoom out.’ This practitioner stated, ‘it is like convergent versus divergent thinking where divergent thinking is done at strategy level and convergent thinking is done at EIA level. There is more scope for creative thinking at strategy level because you remove all the confines.’

A few interviewees acknowledged the need to start the assessments earlier in the process, one CIA practitioner described, ‘the EIA process currently starts too far along in the project’s development when the design is already decided meaning it is harder to make a difference.’

One EIA manager described the potential for the cyclical process to be harnessed for climate action noting ‘EIA procedures are supposed to be cyclical, so when impacts are determined the feedback for improvement is fed back into the design and enhancements are made.’ Another described the importance of tracking mitigation as part of this process, whereby mitigation may be designed into the project but needs to be captured in the CIA. This same EIA manager noted ‘often a design is already developed by the time it gets to the EIA stage and the aim is to get the EIA delivered as quick as possible rather than taking the time to feed back into the design which leads to the mitigation being constrained.’

One CIA practitioner noted the potential for EIA to be used ‘as an in’ for climate action in the built environment, stating ‘the EIA process is not the most forward thinking but it is the way to enable the conversation, which can then lead to action. The process is a way to start meaningful conversation with design teams and with the developer.’

Project Dependencies

The project dependencies were discussed in several interviews. One EIA manager noted ‘climate action on projects is starting to happen in recent times but it depends on the client and the project.’ There were differences specified between public and private sector by a few interviewees. One developer explained ‘the private sector is driven by market expectations and return on investment. They are usually willing to take new technologies or approaches on board because they want that market differentiation, whereas the public sector is constrained by procurement.’

Another EIA manager highlighted ‘controversial projects such as data centres can be more willing to incorporate climate mitigation or adaptation measures as a means of ‘de-risking’ the project.’ Similarly, a developer explained that developers can be driven by fear in terms of meeting targets,

but that this can lead to ‘developers aiming for the most simplistic approach to reducing emissions which is not necessarily the best approach.’

Several interviewees highlighted the importance of budget constraints in determining the level of climate action on a project. One developer noted, ‘project budgets are very tied in with the mitigation because this is where the drive for developers will be constrained or not.’ Another interviewee noted that even if a developer is worried about costs, you still need to put forward suggestions for improvement, however, ‘you need to remember the scope of an EIA and the confines you are working in. Therefore, the design options assessment (before the EIA, when picking the scheme design) should be used to make the big, transformative changes to reduce climate impacts.’

Planning versus Implementation

There were issues related to planning versus implementation discussed in the interviews. It was acknowledged by one CIA practitioner that ‘there is very little advice or guidance on climate mitigation compared to other environmental disciplines.’ This practitioner explained that it is necessary for project EIA and design teams to undertake research or find examples from other countries to figure out how to make improvements.

A key issue that arose across different disciplines and roles was related to the reliance on the contractor. One EIA manager noted that ‘often mitigation at planning is not feasible due to the potential for conflict with contractors. Design enhancements could be incentivised through design and build contracts by putting in requirements for climate action.’ Another noted that there is too much reliance on the contractor, ‘it would be good if there was guidance or standards in place for the contractor especially relating to materials.’

Similarly, a CIA practitioner acknowledged the need for policies and guidance to facilitate agreements with contractors but added ‘there needs to be a better understanding on what mitigation means from a contractors’ perspective.’ Another CIA practitioner highlighted that ‘there is a lot of obligation on the contractor to work within a low margin (tight budget and time constraints) and it means that they are often not willing to take risks on a project.’

A developer explained that ‘EIAR mitigation needs to be written into contract stage or you cannot be sure it will happen’ alluding to the potential for differences seen in action compared to what is considered at planning stage. This developer also explained that ‘sustainability ratings such as the

Housing Performance Index include carbon requirements that require buy-in from the contractor. Putting these requirements in at contractor stage is better than doing it during planning because you are closer to the construction feasibility.’ One of the designers also noted ‘there might be a discrepancy between what is assessed at CIA and what actually happens.’

One CIA practitioner highlighted that there is currently no way of measuring the impact once the project is implemented or checking the mitigation measures, stating ‘we do not actually have a means of knowing if the mitigation is successful.’ This practitioner also highlighted that in Denmark they set carbon targets (like carbon budgets) at project level. Another CIA practitioner explained that emissions reductions are easier to implement than adaptation solutions as carbon reductions are measurable which ‘is not so much the case for resilience – the climate risk assessment has to inform the adaptation solutions.’

Policy

The implications of policy were discussed in detail in many of the interviews. The importance of aligning the project objectives to policy was noted by several interviewees. One EIA manager noted that it is ‘particularly critical for setting the project objectives because they ultimately need to align to government targets.’ Similarly, another EIA manager noted, ‘you need to consider policy from the outset of all projects anyway because otherwise they will not get through planning. You must show your scheme is aligned to planning and policy objectives.’ One designer noted that the assessment should utilise policy more closely, ‘provided policies are set out so that they are achievable on the ground.’ This designer recommended that this be done qualitatively rather than just quantitatively, as it is not possible to entirely predict the outcome of a certain policy measure at project level.

It was acknowledged across all groups that interpreting national scale policies at project level was a challenge. One CIA practitioner noted that ‘we rely too much on policies at national level, which do not relate to project level.’ A developer noted ‘it is very hard to quantify how you are contributing towards them (policy targets).’ Another developer took this further by explaining, ‘policy development takes a top-down approach, but the only way to do a climate assessment is bottom-up.’ This developer recommended that the allocation of carbon budgets be changed to project level (after the allocation by sector).

Similarly, a CIA practitioner recommended that ‘different activities need to be tiered down to project level as the targets are all very high-level at the moment.’ Another CIA practitioner recommended that ‘this must be addressed at city plan level, with a demonstration of emissions reductions with tangible interventions,’ that can be interpreted on projects. A developer also recommended that ‘corporate strategy can be used to interpret the policy and act as the vehicle between policy level and project level. The corporate strategy should be built from the ground up so can act to bring down targets to the organisation which then brought down to projects.’

The use of carbon budgets was discussed in detail with several interviewees. One designer mentioned that ‘if there was a project level carbon budget it would be really useful for influencing the design as you would have something to work towards.’ A CIA practitioner felt that the current approach of comparing the emissions from a project to a national carbon budget is not meaningful as ‘the % contribution of the scheme will always be tiny and will always result in a small relative impact.’ This practitioner explained that this method is only used for compliance purposes (in the UK) rather than using the carbon budgets in a more ambitious sense. Another interviewee brought to light that ‘there are longer term impacts beyond carbon budgets whereby the budget timelines are finite and new projects last decades.’

Other legislative and compliance implications were discussed. One climate strategy practitioner noted that ‘practitioners are typically of a science or engineering background and know their discipline really well, but a huge part of the EIA process is consumed with legislative issues.’ Similarly, one designer noted that ‘legislation is fine, but we need to understand how to work towards it.’ On the other side of this, one interviewee noted that ‘various policy targets such as transport targets, national development plans and the Climate Action Plan are all incompatible and contradict each other,’ which pose challenges when undertaking the CIA.

Some interviewees also acknowledged the importance of legislation in enabling climate action in the built environment. One climate strategy practitioner noted that there are disclosure requirements coming down the line for developers which should drive climate action, stating ‘how resilient assets are in the built environment will improve when there are legal obligations for disclosing.’ A developer noted that construction regulations need to change to facilitate mitigation and adaptation giving the example, ‘mass timber has been constrained in Ireland because of Part B (fire) of the regulations and until they change there will not be mass timber in Ireland.’

Behavioural and Systems Change

There were issues related to behavioural and systems change discussed by many interviewees, particularly considering the ways in which CIA can inspire climate action in the built environment. One climate strategy practitioner noted that ‘not everyone is motivated by climate change, so we may need to be able to show a win-win for their pocket if financial gain is what motivates people.’ Similarly, a CIA practitioner explained the differences in motivation whereby ‘there is a question as to what is considered a successful project. For practitioners it is a project that lower carbon or does not negatively impact the climate but often for developers a successful project is one that goes ahead.’

Several interviewees acknowledged the importance of demonstrating the benefits of undertaking CIA and implementing mitigation or adaptation solutions. One interviewee noted that ‘long-term change is comprised of lots of small changes added together. We need to demonstrate the benefit for people, so they actually feel like these changes matter.’ On the other side of this, one CIA practitioner stated that ‘climate adaptation can be considered non-essential and can be dropped rather than seeing it as being crucial. Highlighting the wider benefits of climate resilience beyond just the built environment such as for populations and the environment (co-benefits) are very important for pushing it forward.’ This same practitioner also felt that ‘the changing climate sometimes is not taken seriously in Ireland because we are not worried about the changes. However, we really should be considering things like heat and increased dampness.’

The educational potential of CIA was also highlighted by a few interviewees, with one noting ‘CIA also raised awareness by showing people what the impact is, so it can be an educational tool.’ A developer also noted that in relation to introducing climate mitigation and adaptation, ‘there needs to be education and advocacy to make sure everyone is on board. It’s mostly a wider attitude approach. People will get used to it.’

Guidance

The availability and use of guidance documents for CIA was discussed by many of the interviewees. One EIA manager described the changing expectations in terms of climate integration to EIA, stating ‘the demands on EIA have increased now with including climate so the EPA should update their guidance to reflect this.’ Another CIA practitioner noted that, ‘it would be useful to have Irish specific CIA guidance that could be overarching.’

Several EIA managers and CIA practitioners described the lack of guidance relating to introducing climate mitigation and adaptation solutions, as previously noted. Others explained the misconceptions associated with the guidance due to misinterpretation, with one CIA practitioner noting ‘what happens is people take snippets from the guidance and interpret it their own way to suit their agenda.’ Another referred to the significance ratings specifically, ‘people are misinterpreting the guidance and it’s too easily being referred to as not significant.’

Baselines

Climate baselines were referenced in several of the interviews by CIA practitioners and designers, with one practitioner noting ‘the baseline is important because it allows you to measure change.’

One designer explained that the baseline can be misconstrued by creating a scenario that looks worse in terms of climate impacts for the purposes of demonstrating mitigation or reduced impacts. They noted ‘sometimes the baseline scenario is actually a gimmick, maybe there needs to be some kind of pre-assessment that would address what is a realistic baseline scenario.’

Mitigation and Adaptation

The application of mitigation and adaptation solutions were discussed in several interviews across all disciplines. One EIA manager summarised the importance of using mitigation and adaptation to ensure acceptable climate impacts, stating ‘the project outcome must ultimately be reasonable in terms of climate impacts. Otherwise, it raises a question if the project should be going ahead.’

The other drivers for implementing these solutions were also considered with one interviewee noting, ‘there has been more focus on mitigation to date which has been driven by policy.’ Another explained, ‘any work that is being done on new projects is qa\wnowhere near achieving Net Zero.’ Similarly one designer described the challenge of knowing what to aim for in terms of carbon reductions and mitigation, noting ‘when I first started calculating carbon and I was getting out a certain number it was very hard to know if that was good or bad or what I was supposed to be aiming for on a project... it would be good to have guidelines on how to change the design to bring this down.’ Another practitioner noted, ‘we need to improve the process of embedding mitigation.’

The challenges of adopting mitigation solutions were also discussed, with one CIA practitioner describing, ‘at the moment mitigation is being implemented very last minute and you are scrambling around looking for something that you can write some text on.’ Another practitioner recommended that the benefits of mitigation need to be proven to ensure developer buy-in, stating

‘it needs to be demonstrated mitigation with proven benefits and proven reductions because we need to be able to show clients the outcome so they will agree to include it on projects.’

There is also uncertainty regarding how and what to implement, with one practitioner describing this as ‘mitigation once we figure out what that should be brings great opportunity.’ There were some suggestions from several interviewees with one EIA manager recommending that, ‘we need to consider extending the life of the asset to save carbon. We also need more data on the mitigation measures.’ Another CIA practitioner highlighted that adaptation solutions need to be informed by the changing climate, describing that ‘we really should be considering things like heat and increased dampness - for example a lot of homes have glass features, how will do those do in the heat?’ Another practitioner highlighted that some mitigation is out of the control of the project, by providing the example of electric vehicles (EVs) stating, ‘you cannot actually change the EV uptake as part of your project beyond including EV charging stations in your car park.’

Collaboration and Engagement

The importance of collaboration and engagement throughout the CIA process was brought to light in several interviews, with one CIA practitioner summarising this as follows ‘the CIA practitioner is not working in isolation. There should be a strong process for collaboration, working with designers to embed mitigation.’ Another practitioner similarly noted, ‘there needs to be more discussion between planners, designers and contractors.’ A developer described in more detail the ways in which skills and knowledge need to be brought together to assess and reduce impacts, ‘we need to bring different expertise together. There is some very detailed expertise on different areas existing in little silos. There is a job in linking everything together.’

The need for interdisciplinary engagement across the various EIA specialist areas was also highlighted, with one EIA manager posing the questions, ‘how does carbon affect other disciplines and what receptors will feel the impacts of climate change?’ A CIA practitioner described the need for this engagement to take a ‘whole-systems’ approach as follows ‘other disciplines are more open to having conversations about mitigation, for example ecologists contributing to the nature-based solutions.’ Another interviewee took this further by explaining the importance of not solely focusing on carbon as a metric for climate impacts, explaining ‘carbon tunnel vision for these simplistic pathways is also an issue whereby there are carbon targets that need to be met, but there also needs to be considerations for biodiversity and other disciplines.’

For successful collaboration and engagement, there needs to be a willingness from the various disciplines which was discussed by some of the interviewees. One climate strategy practitioner noted that ‘the framing is important for engagement, for example, maybe it needs to be framed as making positive change instead of lowering negative impacts so that people feel they are making a difference.’ A designer also described the need for this cross-collaboration beyond the planning stage, ‘there needs to be buy in across the board and not just at planning. Perhaps this needs to be given a lot of weight at tender stage for all phases of the project.’

Uncertainties

The inherent uncertainties in delivering CIAs were acknowledged by many of the interviewees to varying extents, with one EIA manager explaining that ‘there is a large amount of uncertainty in the data at planning stage.’ This same manager highlights that the data can determine if the assessment will be successful in driving climate action on a project, noting ‘if the assessment is robust enough that you fully understand the impacts then this can be influential, but data is needed to support this which can be challenging to obtain.’ Another EIA manager similarly points out the challenge in gathering data at the early, planning stage of a project, stating that ‘sometimes the detail is not there at the early stages of the project. A lot more real and proper detail is needed to do a thorough assessment.’

One CIA practitioner also brings to light the poor data gathering processes, explaining that ‘there is just not enough data, and we do not start gathering data early enough so can be challenge.’ Another CIA practitioner describes data usage issues as follows ‘the ability to use the data is another challenge whereby there are lots of ranges and uncertainties and how that is incorporated is key.’ This practitioner recommended that CIA procedures should be more focused on developing out the evidence base and filling the data gaps for climate change. One developer also recommended filling data gaps, stating ‘there will be inherent assumptions to fill the data gaps. We need more suppliers to provide data, ideally in the form of an EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) but this is very challenging.’ A designer noted the uncertainties in the data but acknowledged that the numbers do not have to be exact to inform change, ‘even if the carbon numbers are not 100% accurate, they provide good guidance.’

Further to data challenges, some interviewees also described the uncertainties associated with mitigation solutions. One CIA practitioner explained that ‘there is a lack of solutions in this space,

and we do not know the full potential of the technology that's out there.' Another practitioner highlighted the knowledge gap around novel technologies, stating, 'there is a challenge to measure innovation and prove that something new will make improvements, for example biological materials, we really need EPDs developed for these new solutions.' There are also uncertainties associated with changing baseline conditions in future with one interviewee bringing to light that 'there can be challenges associated with population increase, for example, that has nothing to do with the project but will increase carbon emissions when modelled.'

Assessment: Guidance Documents

Overview

A comprehensive list of 9 guidance documents were selected, which concentrate on decarbonisation, adaptation, and EIA for the built environment with varying sectoral scopes. The guidance documents selected for review included the following:

- Institute of Environmental Management and Assessment (IEMA) (2022) Assessing Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Evaluating their Significance;
- IEMA (2020) Environmental Impact Assessment Guide to: Climate Change Resilience & Adaptation;
- PAS2080 Carbon Management Verification (2023);
- European Commission (2021) Technical guidance on the climate proofing of infrastructure in the period 2021-2027;
- European Commission (2013) Guidance on Integrating Climate Change and Biodiversity into Environmental Impact Assessment;
- Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) (2022) Guidelines on the information to be contained in Environmental Impact Assessment Reports;
- Transport Infrastructure Ireland (TII) (2022) Overarching Technical Document - Climate Assessment of Proposed Light Rail, Rural Cycleways and National Roads;
- TII (2022) Climate Assessment of Proposed National Roads – Standard; and
- UKHA (2021) Design Manual for Roads and Bridges Volume 11 Environmental Assessment, Section 3 Environmental Assessment Techniques, Part 14 LA 114 – Climate.

A summarised evidence-informed description of each of the selected guidance documents is provided in **Table 5**, including consideration of institutional context.

Table 5 Overview of Guidance Documents

Document	Source Level	Description
IEMA GHG Guidance (2022)	International (UK source)	The guidance “Assessing Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Evaluating their Significance,” was published in 2022 by IEMA a UK based environmental agency that has international reach. The guidance is overarching, high-level and aimed at EIA and GHG practitioners undertaking CIA for planning. There is no legal imperative to follow the guidance. It covers projects in the built environment. It takes the standpoint of early intervention on projects and assumes the whole project team is on board for optimum sustainability outcomes. The guidance focuses primarily on GHG assessment within the CIA process for EIA only (and excludes resilience). It refers to some UK legislation for EIA and planning not relevant to the Irish context. The expectations in terms of changing market and regulatory conditions are well covered.
IEMA Resilience Guidance (2020)	International (UK source)	The guidance “Environmental Impact Assessment Guide to: Climate Change Resilience and Adaptation,” was published in 2020 by IEMA a UK based environmental agency that has international reach. The guidance is overarching, high-level and aimed at EIA and climate resilience practitioners undertaking CIA for planning. There is no legal imperative to follow the guidance. It covers projects in the built environment. It focuses solely on climate resilience and adaptation within the CIA and EIA process (and excludes GHG assessment). It refers to UK legislation for EIA and planning not relevant to the Irish context.
PAS2080:2023	International (UK source)	The standard PAS2080:2023 for “Carbon Management in Buildings and Infrastructure” was commissioned by the Green Construction Board and facilitated by the British Standard Institution (BSI). It updates the previous 2016 version. It is UK focused but has international reach and substantial recognition within the industry in Ireland (in both planning and design). It is well marketed and has received a lot of attention. It is not focused within the EIA context specifically. It focuses on carbon in the built environment, with the view to aligning the built environment to Net Zero by 2050. It excludes climate resilience. Market expectations are well covered in addition to long term vision to 2050.

Document	Source Level	Description
EU Guidance on Climate Proofing Infrastructure (2021)	EU	<p>This technical guidance published by the European Commission in 2021 covers "climate proofing of infrastructure" which is a process that integrates both climate change mitigation and adaptation measures into the development of infrastructure projects. The term infrastructure includes built systems, assets, and buildings in this instance. The European Commission has a broad reach and is extremely influential in setting standards across the EU but also globally and this guidance is already well known within the industry. The European Commission has scope to influence the surrounding policy landscape to enable the successful implementation of guidance. The guidance aims to facilitate compliance with legislation for several EU funds and aims to be consistent with the Paris Agreement.</p>
EU Climate and Biodiversity into EIA (2013)	EU	<p>This is a European Commission guidance on "Integrating Climate Change and Biodiversity into Environmental Impact Assessment." The European Commission has a broad reach and is influential across European Member States but also across other regions. The guidance is EIA focused covering the integration of both climate and biodiversity at a high-level, with an EU context in terms of the policy landscape. The guidance was published in 2013 and is therefore slightly out of date but well known in the industry in terms of the high-level introductory concepts. It could be assumed that most CIA practitioners in Ireland are familiar with this guidance.</p>
EPA EIA Guidance (2022)	Ireland	<p>The guidelines "Guidelines on the information to be contained in Environmental Impact Assessment Reports," were published by the Irish EPA in 2022 and are extremely influential in Ireland. They provide an interpretation of the European EIA legislation for the Irish context in practical terms for EIA practitioners. This guidance updates the previous draft (2017) version. It can be assumed that it is well known and used by all EIA practitioners in Ireland. It refers to all EIA disciplines including climate. This guidance focuses on compliance in terms of the legislation rather than market expectations.</p>

Document	Source Level	Description
TII Overarching Technical Document (2022)	Ireland (sectoral)	<p>This Overarching Technical Document titled “Climate Assessment of Proposed Light Rail, Rural Cycleways and National Roads” was prepared by TII for national roads, light rail and rural cycleways (of which TII manage), published in December 2022, for schemes being assessed outside of the statutory planning process. The document is technical in nature and specific to the named transport infrastructure projects in Ireland. It covers both carbon impacts and climate risk. The document will be influential in Ireland whereby any of TIIs proposed transport schemes will be expected to be assessed against this guidance. TII are a well renowned within the industry for standard setting and will likely set the precedence for other transport schemes and potentially other infrastructure schemes in Ireland with this guidance. TII themselves will create enabling conditions for alignment with their guidance for the benefit of their own schemes.</p>
TII Roads Standard (2022)	Ireland (sectoral)	<p>This standard (“Climate Assessment of Proposed National Roads”) was published by TII in 2022 and available for use on the TII publications website. Similar to the Overarching Technical Document, TII will likely set the precedence for other transport schemes in Ireland and will create enabling conditions for alignment with this standard for the benefit of their own schemes. This standard should be used in conjunction with the TII Overarching Technical Document but is specifically geared at proposed National Roads Schemes that go through the statutory planning process and are subject to EIA. It includes both greenhouse gas assessment and climate change risk assessment.</p>
UK Highways England LA114 Climate (2021)	UK (sectoral)	<p>This document “Design Manual for Roads and Bridges Volume 11 Environmental Assessment, Section 3 Environmental Assessment Techniques, Part 14 LA 114 – Climate” was published by Highways England in 2021. It comprises the requirements for assessing climate impacts and greenhouse gases on highways in the UK. It includes both greenhouse gases and climate resilience across all stages of the projects (construction, operation, and maintenance) which can be incorporated into EIA. It is a well-regarded document within the industry particularly</p>

Document	Source Level	Description
		in the UK but is generally known in Ireland (though may no longer be influential in the Irish context given that TII has released standards). It was first published in 2019 and updated in 2021.

Scoring

The best performing guidance documents when rated against the developed framework include the TII Overarching Technical Document, followed by the TII National Roads Standard which are the first CIA standards developed for the Irish context and are sector specific. These are followed consecutively by the IEMA GHG guidance (which improved a previous 2020 version of the document), PAS2080 standard, the EU Climate Proofing guidelines and the IEMA Resilience guidance which all provide overarching guidance intended to be cross-sectoral and relevant for all disciplines.

The EPA EIA guidance scores relatively poorly in terms of addressing CIA challenges and opportunities. However, it is an important guidance document in Ireland for introducing key concepts and setting the baseline approach to EIA in general. The UK Highways England LA114 guidance for roads schemes and the EU Climate and Biodiversity EIA guidance also score relatively poorly, which is due to being outdated in terms of policy and evolving best practice. Though it should be noted that the EU guidance introduces important concepts on stakeholder engagement and interdisciplinary collaboration that the newer guidance documents fail to address.

The challenges and opportunities performed equally against the framework, with consistent poor performance across several areas (design enhancement, mitigation and adaptation solutions, cumulative impacts, and significance ratings). Often to maximise opportunities, it is necessary to overcome some inherent challenges, so the two are not mutually exclusive, as previously discussed. The effectiveness score was comparatively much better, which demonstrates that the guidance documents are communicating the desired information successfully but have not been intended to address some of key challenges and opportunities. In general opportunities were not scoring well due to a lack of tangible actions to reduce climate impacts, particularly design improvements and solutions which is interlinked with mitigation and adaptation. The high-level concepts were well covered, as revealed by the assessment framework, but failed to translate into actionable measures.

It is acknowledged that the appraisal of guidance documents undertaken using the framework may not be an entirely fair assessment given that the criteria were kept uniform for each document even though they serve slightly different purposes. However, this uniform assessment process acts as a needs and gaps analysis by demonstrating how the guidance documents perform comparatively and together. Similarly, there appears to be a place for overarching guidance as well as sectoral guidance for specific project types – but if they are to co-exist, they must work to complement each other (which should be demonstrated when compared side by side). There is currently no overarching document specific to the Irish context. Overarching guidance documents are needed to set the high-level concepts and fundamental principles that should be common to the various sectors to ensure a level of consistency and quality. To ensure the expected actions are not misinterpreted, such a document needs to be followed with sectoral guidance (for example roads, infrastructure, buildings, power, manufacturing etc) that can detail specifics and tangible actions for construction and design solutions.

From the interviews, it is evident that there are a lot of areas in which people are unclear in terms of CIA approaches, which is largely consistent with the low RAG scoring on some criteria in the assessment framework.

The scoring and short justification for each guidance document according to the assessment framework is provided in **Tables 6 – 14** with a summary of the scores for all documents provided in **Table 15**.

Table 6 IEMA GHG Guidance (2022) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings		There is an entire section on significance which aims to clarify previous uncertainty, acknowledging the inevitability of some level of impact. There are examples given of project types and their significance.
Baselines		Some information on defining baselines, providing list of sources of information but remains high-level.
Policy integration		The guidance refers to proportioning a carbon budget or other suitable contextual information relating to policy mostly, with types of information listed (but a slightly UK focused).

Criterion	Score	Justification
Mitigation and adaptation		There is a conceptual, high-level approach to mitigation provided, with recommendation for a ‘carbon coordinator’ to promote emissions reductions. Mitigation section is relatively light, and lacks detail on implementation, and no mention of monitoring.
Cumulative impacts		There is reference to the challenge associated with climate being a global receptor and the need to contextualise impacts using policy. The advice is high-level and could be open to interpretation.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘challenges’ is amber.
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		There is a lack of detail on practical implementation and improving designs to reduce carbon emissions.
Early-stage project input		The challenge of limited information at early stages is noted with a recommendation to undertake stakeholder engagement, however no advice on the ‘how’ is provided.
Interdisciplinarity		There is recommendation to collaborate with design teams undertaking sustainability ratings (such as BREEAM) on the GHG assessment but remains quite high-level. Other EIA disciplines are not detailed.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is red.
Effectiveness		
Influence		Overarching guidance with some influence, however, it is not specific to the Irish context, refer to Table 5 .
Clarity		The concepts are well explained, including some of the more challenging aspects of CIA procedures. There is a clear scope set out.
Usability		The document follows the EIA procedural stages which is useful for practitioners. The communication and reporting section is quite practical, however, most of the guidance remains high-level and mainly conceptual rather than focusing on tangible actions and implementation.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is amber.

Table 7 IEMA Resilience Guidance (2020) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings		There is limited direction given on significance ratings, referring to existing procedures and leaving the approach open to interpretation.
Baselines		There is detail on approaching the climate baseline, including future baseline projections. There is detail on sourcing data, including an example data set (though UK focused). There is an appendix dedicated to selecting future climate scenarios.
Policy integration		There is some policy covered in an appendix, but it does not fully cover the integration with policy. However, it should be noted that resilience is not pushed as much at the policy level.
Mitigation and adaptation		The adaptation solutions are very high-level with a lack of tangible actions (more high-level than the GHG IEMA guidance). There could be more detail on how to use climate data with solutions focus.
Cumulative impacts		There is limited direction given on cumulative impacts, referring to existing procedures and leaving the approach open to interpretation.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘challenges’ is red.
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		There is mention of using climate risk assessment to incorporate resilience into the design, including a conceptual approach to iterative improvements. There is one example but could include more detail in terms of implementation and tangible actions.
Early-stage project input		There is a full chapter dedicated to steps on early-stage input prior to the commencement of EIA processes.
Interdisciplinarity		Guidance on interaction and engagement with other disciplines is completely lacking.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is amber.

Criterion	Score	Justification
Effectiveness		
Influence	Amber	Overarching guidance with some influence, however, it is not specific to the Irish context, refer to Table 5 . It makes clear that sector specific guidance should also be used.
Clarity	Green	A section is included on ‘how to use this document’ in addition to definitions of the key principles at the beginning. The concepts that are included are well explained.
Usability	Green	The guidance follows the EIA procedural stages which is useful for practitioners. The appendices include useful examples, templates, and definitions for project roles. It takes quite a practical approach.
Overall score	Green	The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is green.

Table 8 PAS2080:2023 Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings	Red	This standard is not EIA focused; therefore, it does not discuss EIA terms like significance ratings.
Baselines	Green	It covers baselines and target setting including implementation (such as defined governance) and practical, tangible actions.
Policy integration	Amber	There is guidance in terms of support for governments, regulators, and financiers which is out of scope for CIA. It covers the importance of the policy agenda in driving and aligning with outcomes.
Mitigation and adaptation	Amber	High-level, conceptual guidance on decarbonisation principles including decision-making, co-benefits, monitoring, and value chain engagement, taking a practical action-focused approach. However, it does not detail specific mitigation measures (including design, materials, etc).
Cumulative impacts	Red	This standard is not EIA focused; therefore, it does not discuss EIA terms like significance ratings.
Overall score	Amber	The overall score for ‘challenges’ is amber.

Criterion	Score	Justification
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		Despite detail on potential emission sources there is no guidance on the ‘how’ with the implementation of emissions removals left open to interpretation.
Early-stage project input		There is acknowledgement throughout the document that early-stage project input should be leveraged, however, it does not cover an approach in detail.
Interdisciplinarity		An integrated approach for GHG assessment of buildings and infrastructure (as well as projects and programmes) is provided There is detail on the interaction and co-benefits between carbon and other disciplines such as ecosystems, land use and circular economy.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is amber.
Effectiveness		
Influence		PAS2080 aims to set the 'overarching principles' for the built environment and is influential within industry, refer to Table 5 .
Clarity		There is a definition of terms provided to cover cross-disciplinary terminology. It clearly sets out the scope of the updated version of the standard compared to the previous. The concepts are explained clearly throughout the document including high-level ideas (such as influence vs control on emissions).
Usability		There is an emphasis on the construction supply chain which is useful and practical but in terms of EIA there may be ambiguity on how to integrate this into the EIA process itself. Some guidance remains high-level and lacking in tangible actions. There are roles and actions defined for projects which is useful for project teams.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is green.

Table 9 EU Guidance on Climate Proofing Infrastructure (2021) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings		The significance ratings as they relate to CIA are not well-covered in this guidance, with limited details and only high-level acknowledgement of the significance of impacts.
Baselines		There is detail on climate baselines (including future projections), however, there is limited information on carbon baselining approaches that would be applicable for EIA procedures.
Policy integration		There is detail on the alignment with EU policies including appendices dedicated to the integration to environmental legislation.
Mitigation and adaptation		There high-level concepts for mitigation and adaptation solutions provided, including references to other methodology (such as carbon ‘scopes’). There is further detail on adaptation solutions provided in an appendix for EIA, however, mitigation is not well covered and the ‘how’ is not fully addressed.
Cumulative impacts		Cumulative impacts are covered in an appendix including some detail on evolving baselines however, it remains high-level.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘challenges’ is amber.
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		There is an acknowledgement for some of the adaptation challenges but there is a lack of solutions to go with them, and limited information on carbon reductions. Any information is high-level and lacks the tangible actions that can be applied by designers.
Early-stage project input		There is high-level detail on early-stage project input including information on EIA screening in the appendix, though this could be expanded.
Interdisciplinarity		There is not a lot of detail provided on interactions between various disciplines (other than a brief reference to impact chains) and cross collaboration.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is red.

Criterion	Score	Justification
Effectiveness		
Influence		The guidance is highly influential in the EU given the scope of the European Commission to influence Member States and the policy landscape, refer to Table 5 .
Clarity		The scope of the guidance is clearly set out, and it contains definitions of terms and summaries of key concepts. There is a lot of key information contained in the appendices which makes the structure more challenging to follow.
Usability		There are practical learnings from past projects, useful examples, and questions for practitioners however, the detail remains quite high-level. Some of the recommended approaches may not be deemed appropriate for use in EIA procedures (for example using carbon ‘scopes’).
Overall score		The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is amber.

Table 10 EU Climate and Biodiversity EIA Guidance (2013) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings		The guidance does not cover significance ratings for CIA in any detail.
Baselines		There is coverage of evolving future baselines relevant for climate however, there is a lack of further detail relating to baseline development.
Policy integration		There is a detailed background on the EIA Directive is provides, as well as a further policy context however, much of the policy is now out of date.
Mitigation and adaptation		The guidance explains both mitigation and adaptation (including maladaptation). Mitigation and solutions are very light touch, but monitoring and adaptive management is well covered.
Cumulative impacts		The cumulative impacts are better explained from a biodiversity perspective rather than climate change.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘challenges’ is red.

Criterion	Score	Justification
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		This guidance does not cover tangible actions to reduce climate impacts through design in any detail.
Early-stage project input		The need for stakeholder engagement early in the EIA process is emphasized. The importance of the scoping stage is highlighted; however, it would be useful to give detail on the actions required prior to the screening stage of before.
Interdisciplinarity		The guidance is focused on interdisciplinary collaboration throughout, particularly between biodiversity and climate but also other disciplines. It considers the complexity of relationships conceptually and includes questions to help with collaboration amongst the team. There is detailed guidance on stakeholder engagement throughout the project phases, including follow-up and inputting to mitigation and adaptation. It also covers the inter-relationship between mitigation and adaptation.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is amber.
Effectiveness		
Influence		The guidance was published in 2013 by the European Commission, with influence across the EU and an integration with the policy landscape. However, the guidance was published in 2013 and is outdated in some respects, refer to Table 5 .
Clarity		There are detailed definitions of terms and an executive summary provided. The content is clearly described with summaries, step-by-step approaches, and concise explanations.
Usability		The guidance follows the EIA stages, with examples, and strong practical advice in terms of stakeholder engagement, collaboration and communicating uncertainty. The closeness to EIA applicability becomes vague at times, and the coverage of most of the challenges is weak from a practitioner’s perspective.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is amber.

Table 11 EPA EIA Guidance (2022) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings	Yellow	There is substantial detail on EIA process of assigning significance, but it is not easily interpreted for climate.
Baselines	Red	The information provided on baselines is not relevant for climate impacts.
Policy integration	Red	The guidance does not refer to the wider policy landscape as it is designed to be effective over the long term. It aligns closely with the EIA Directive; however, this is not sufficient for CIA.
Mitigation and adaptation	Red	The conceptual mitigation approach is similar to the conceptual approaches applied to CIA specifically, however, there is limited detail and a lack of practical guidance.
Cumulative impacts	Red	The guidance on cumulative impacts is not relevant for climate impacts given the global context (though acknowledging transboundary consultation is provided).
Overall score	Red	The overall score for ‘challenges’ is red.
Opportunities		
Design enhancements	Red	The guidelines do not cover design enhancements or the improvement process applicable to CIA in any detail.
Early-stage project input	Red	Early consultation emphasized - but detail on cross disciplinary approach lacking.
Interdisciplinarity	Yellow	The guidance does not separate climate from other environmental disciplines. There is a clear approach provided to address interactions which is a commonly applied approach – but does not go into detail.
Overall score	Red	The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is red.
Effectiveness		
Influence	Green	The guidance is highly influential in Ireland, providing the ‘baseline’ knowledge to most CIA and EIA practitioners and ensuring compliance with EU legislation, refer to Table 5 .
Clarity	Green	There is a definition of terms provided and the concepts for a high-quality EIAR are well explained with examples from case law (though lacking in climate specific examples).

Criterion	Score	Justification
Usability		It is designed to be effective over the long term, with practical guidance in terms of reporting, however it remains high-level and does not give detail in terms of implementation.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is green.

Table 12 TII Overarching Technical Document (2022) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings		There are clear definitions provided for significance ratings, including for beneficial impacts (though more limited). It links into IEMA guidance whilst providing some additional information on contextualising emissions for the Irish context (with carbon budgets). For resilience the significance ratings align to the outcomes of the risk assessment scenarios with is useful.
Baselines		There is detail on do-minimum versus do-something scenarios. There is some detail on data collection (with practical checklists) but there could be more guidance on data interpretation, particularly for climate risk. TII recommend using their own emissions and carbon tools.
Policy integration		There is a lot of detail provided on the climate policy context for Ireland, which includes reference to other guidance documents such IEMA, EU, and PAS2080. The long-term alignment to Net Zero is regarded.
Mitigation and adaptation		A conceptual mitigation hierarchy from the other guidance documents is referenced for reducing GHG emissions. There is detail in the monitoring section, however there could be further detail provided on the ‘how’ in terms of emissions reductions and adaptation solutions.
Cumulative impacts		The cumulative impacts are light touch for carbon emissions, relying solely on contextualization. The cumulative impacts for climate risks are more detailed, recommending a consideration of

Criterion	Score	Justification
		the wider transport network (which may be out of scope for an EIA).
Overall score		The overall score for ‘challenges’ is amber.
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		The guidance does not cover design enhancements or tangible actions to reduce climate impacts in any detail.
Early-stage project input		There is detail provided on assessment approaches prior to EIA stages commencing, including the needs assessment which has the potential to be transformative in reducing climate impacts.
Interdisciplinarity		The differences between mitigation and adaptation is well covered including tips on integrating the GHG and climate risk assessment, however, interactions with other disciplines (including EIA disciplines) is not covered.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is amber.
Effectiveness		
Influence		The guidance is influential for transport infrastructure in Ireland, being the first CIA guidance specific to the Irish context, refer to Table 5 . However, as it is specific to transport infrastructure it may not translate well to the wider built environment.
Clarity		It is a clear document with extensive detail on conducting CIA of transport infrastructure projects including all project phases, ensuring there is limited scope for misinterpretation.
Usability		There are practical checklists, instructions for the CIA practitioner and additional resources (such as carbon calculation tools) that complement the guidance. The instructions for the GHG and climate risk assessments are both detailed and methodical and align to other ‘overarching’ guidance and standards.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is green.

Table 13 TII Roads Standard (2022) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings		This standard provides clear definitions on the significance ratings, including the benefits of the scheme, linking to the Irish context.
Baselines		There is good information on defining the study area, boundaries, and scope from the early stages including data for baseline development. There is detail on the do-minimum and do-something. However, there could be more guidance on data interpretation, particularly for climate risk.
Policy integration		There is a lot of detail provided on the climate policy context for Ireland and National Roads including detail on TII’s policies and standards. The alignment to net zero policy is demonstrated, including a comparison of emissions trajectories and a worked example utilising carbon budgets to contextualise emissions.
Mitigation and adaptation		The mitigation hierarchy from the other guidance documents is referenced. There is a lack of detail on practical implementation, mitigation, or potential focus areas like those included in the Overarching Technical Document.
Cumulative impacts		The cumulative impacts are covered but remain high-level which leaves a risk of misinterpretation.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘challenges’ is amber.
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		This standard does not cover design enhancements or tangible actions to reduce climate impacts in any detail.
Early-stage project input		There is detail provided on assessment approaches prior to EIA stages commencing, including the needs assessment which has the potential to be transformative in reducing climate impacts.
Interdisciplinarity		It includes an overview of the various disciplines that are required to feed into the assessment and how exactly the disciplines overlap with climate. There need for a collaborative approach is acknowledged.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is amber.

Criterion	Score	Justification
Effectiveness		
Influence		The guidance is influential for National Roads in Ireland, being the first type of standard specific to the Irish context, refer to Table 5 . However, as it is specific to National Roads it may not translate well to the wider built environment.
Clarity		It is a clear document with instructions on using the document. There is clear methodology provided for CIA on National Roads projects with limited scope for misinterpretation.
Usability		There are templates and worked examples which are useful for practitioners. The climate risk example includes interactions with other disciplines which is very strong. There could be more tangible actions includes on mitigation and adaptation solutions.
Overall score		The overall score for 'effectiveness' is green.

Table 14 UK Highways England LA114 Climate Guidance (2021) Scoring

Criterion	Score	Justification
Challenges		
Significance ratings		The significance of the impact is only acknowledged from a climate risk perspective and is not clearly applicable for CIA in an EIA process. It is not covered for the GHG assessment at all.
Baselines		The guidance provides data sources for baseline development and explains the do-something and do-minimum scenarios. However, the explanation lacks detail from a CIA perspective and the proposed approach is not well structured.
Policy integration		There is a policy context provided but focused on the UK context which is not relevant for Ireland, however, there is reference to the EIA Directive. There is some guidance on the varying timelines for carbon budgets and how to report against the multiple budgets.
Mitigation and adaptation		There are no adaptation approaches provided. There is a requirement for monitoring which is beneficial from a mitigation

Criterion	Score	Justification
		perspective, however, the mitigation approaches are high-level only.
Cumulative impacts		This guidance does not cover cumulative impacts relevant to CIA in any detail.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘challenges’ is red.
Opportunities		
Design enhancements		This guidance does not cover design enhancements for reducing climate impacts.
Early-stage project input		There is an acknowledgement that there is the greatest potential for the reduction of GHGs early in the project. However, despite this, the guidance begins at the scoping stage with no detail on screening stage or steps prior to EIA.
Interdisciplinarity		The integration with other environmental assessment documents is required. The importance of collaborating with other disciplines is recommended though, detailed advice is not provided.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘opportunities’ is amber.
Effectiveness		
Influence		This guidance has some influence particularly for road and infrastructure schemes; however, it is not specific to the Irish context, and may no longer be influential due to new guidance becoming more relevant (TII and IEMA) refer to Table 5 .
Clarity		There are definitions provided at the beginning and a clear scope for the document. Some of the explanations remain vague and open to interpretation due to lack of detail, despite being a sector specific guidance document (roads).
Usability		The guidance follows project phases that can be transferrable to EIA. There is detail on life-cycle stages and connections to other guidance documents provided which is useful for practitioners. There is reference to utilising certain types of tools but limited detail or resources provided. There is a lack of tangible actions.
Overall score		The overall score for ‘effectiveness’ is amber.

Table 15 Guidance Documents Scoring Summary

Criteria	IEMA GHG	EPA EIA	IEMA Resilience	PAS2080	TII OTD	TII Roads	EU Climate Proofing	EU Climate & Biodiversity	UK LA114
Challenges									
Significance ratings	Green	Yellow	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
Baselines	Yellow	Red	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Policy integration	Green	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow
Mitigation/adaptation	Yellow	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Cumulative impacts				Red		Yellow			
Overall Score Challenges	Yellow	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red
Opportunities									
Design enhancements	Red	Red	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Early-stage input	Red	Red	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Interdisciplinarity	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Green	Yellow
Overall Score Opportunities	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Red
Effectiveness									
Influence	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Yellow
Clarity	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow
Usability	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Overall Score Effectiveness	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow

Discussion

The findings from the various components of this research have been mapped in **Figure 4** below, demonstrating the inter-relationships between the findings. The consolidated findings have been categorised into three key thematic groupings (shown in the blue, green and purple colour) which can be traced back to findings from different stages of the research (indicated with matching colours). The blue indicates findings related to ‘policies and procedures,’ the green indicates findings related to ‘data and implementation,’ and the purple indicates findings related to ‘interdisciplinary collaboration.’

Figure 4 Relationship between Research Findings

Consolidated Insights

This research brings together insights from literature, interviews conducted with industry professionals, and the bespoke assessment of relevant guidance documents, to develop consolidated learnings for CIA, as shown in **Figure 4** above. The findings from the various phases of the research informed the subsequent phases, ensuring a well-rounded approach that maintains a focus on the practical application of CIA. The results of the assessment reveal some patterns and weaknesses in the available guidance that need to be considered in light of the findings from the interviews and existing literature. The research was focused on the Irish context, but the insights could be applicable to other European and UK contexts.

The findings fulfill the research objectives (set out in the ‘Introduction’ section), by identifying the challenges associated with current CIA approaches in Ireland and determining the ways in which the ‘best practice’ approaches captured in the available guidance documents address these issues. Based on these consolidated learnings, recommendations are provided in the next section (‘Recommendations’) to improve these ‘best practice’ approaches.

It is the consensus within literature and throughout the interviews that climate action in the built environment is not happening to its full potential. Whilst EIA is considered the entry point for facilitating sustainable development and climate action, as aptly pointed out in several interviews (complementary to literature) - it is paramount that we harness CIA as an important tool for driving climate action within planning and development. This must start by addressing the evident issues and weaknesses and by utilising CIA guidance documents as a lever between policy targets and action on the ground.

The consolidated insights were grouped into three categories by examining the themes across the research findings. The three thematic groupings include (1) policies and procedures, (2) data and implementation, and (3) interdisciplinary collaboration, as shown in **Figure 4**. These three groupings are inter-related whereby the intersection between these groupings must be comprehended to both understand the extent of the inter-relationships and approach needed to make improvements to the CIA procedures. Therefore, it is essential to view the consolidated insights through a lens that looks ‘beyond-compliance’ or, in other words, a perspective that does not focus solely on compliance to be able to see the big picture and contextual influence relevant

to CIA. This ‘beyond-compliance’ lens is explained here before discussing each thematic grouping in detail.

‘Beyond Compliance’

The literature primarily focused on the policies and procedures associated with CIA including climate integration to EIA. However, there was some recognition in the literature for the need to shift EIA procedures to encompass transformational purpose (Loomis et al, 2022) and move away from the tick-box approach to assessment (IES, 2023). This is important for enabling the successful execution of CIA as part of the EIA process whereby CIA is not currently achieving the desired outcomes for projects (namely to capture and reduce climate impacts). To do this, the focus needs to be shifted away from a compliance tunnel vision to a lens beyond compliance (for example, EPA (2023)). This compliance tunnel vision typically occurs when developers aim for the bare minimum to get through the planning hurdle as quickly as possible.

The interview responses highlighted the legislative fears held by practitioners and developers whereby the planning system can be ‘consumed with legislative issues.’ Whilst legislation is important to drive action, the focus on compliance can lead to complacency whereby there is no drive to harness the transformative thinking required to establish change. This type of complacency can cause developers and design teams to lose sight of the big picture and forget about continuous improvement or optimising the design for sustainability outcomes.

The literature has also documented examples of non-compliance against legislative requirements in place for the benefit of reducing climate impacts (Adric and Al-Ghamdi, 2018), which suggests that this complacency may not only be due to the compliance focus but also a deeper cultural issue. On the other hand, there is a risk that the developer or project team may attempt to play a ‘compliance game’ by undermining thresholds or creating a false baseline scenario to allude to mitigation efforts. This ‘compliance game’ may also arise due to the process of justification of the impacts which often takes precedence over reducing the impacts in current CIA procedures. This is particularly the case on riskier projects where the CIA is used as a method of ‘de-risking’ as discussed throughout the interviews. Furthermore, the depoliticising of the EIA process, as recommended in literature (Bond et al, 2020) would also be interconnected with this compliance game.

A key finding, from consolidating the insights from this research, is that the EIA process should not be considered in isolation, but appreciation given to the wider context and the forces interacting with CIA to determine its successful application. A reframing is crucial for CIA procedures which need to be treated differently to other environmental topics. There is a significant challenge in discerning if and to what extent a global climate impact is attributable (IPCC, 2007) to an individual activity or project, with the increase in the GHG concentrations in the atmosphere resulting from many cumulative sources around the globe (Stone et al, 2013). This “drop in the ocean” problem is the most obvious for project-level EIAs (Mayer, 2019). The quantification and management of climate impacts is a complex and dynamic process, with no single metric (not even carbon dioxide (Achakulwisut et al, 2022) and many inter-relationships across disciplines (Dastjerdi and Nasrabadi, 2022) including different concepts, terms, and standards spanning the varied requirements of different disciplines (Stone et al, 2013).

When project teams are primarily focused on meeting compliance targets for CIA, they can focus too much on the procedures and lose sight of the contextual importance of the impacts on the global climate receptor. As such, it is not a surprise that the development of a comprehensive assessment approach suitable for the EIA process is proving a difficult task, coming with many uncertainties and drawbacks as demonstrated from the interviews and assessment framework.

Further ‘beyond compliance’ perspectives are provided throughout this section, under each of the three themes, demonstrating how the inter-section between thematic groupings brings additional insight, as discussed (see **Figure 4**).

Policies and Procedures

Reframing

To ensure that CIA is properly linked to the big picture, the thorough consideration of interrelationships and cumulative effects is necessary, as recommended by literature (Destjerdi et al (2022) and Jirricka-Purrer et al (2018)). This includes stakeholder engagement and holistic framing of climate impacts and solutions. It also requires some external help through the creation of enabling conditions in policy which can be facilitated by SEA. SEA is widely recognised in the literature (Posas, 2011 and, Gunn and Noble, 2009) as being a potential mechanism to better integrate climate into EIA. However, this is not happening in practice, reflected in the findings of this research whereby none of the interviewees discussed the implications of SEA (it does not

appear on practitioners' radar). To change this, SEAs need to develop an enhanced approach to climate change assessment that incorporates more bottom-up perspectives than the current best practice (EPA, 2019). Furthermore, EIA approaches need to consider SEA as a reference or starting point and leverage its findings to inform the early stages of the design or alternatives at project level.

Similarly, there is still a need for better integration of policy to CIA with ambiguity remaining amongst practitioners despite some efforts to provide instruction on this within several guidance documents. This was evident from the interview discussions with practitioners whereby different interviewees had different takes on what policy integration comprises. However, much of this ambiguity is driven by the policies themselves. There is an inconsistent vision across the policy landscape and a lack of clarity on how to achieve top-down targets at project level due to the lack of bottom-up guidance or consideration when setting the targets, as discussed in the interviews. In addition, there are conflicting policies (for example, growth targets) that do not support the achievement of climate targets which makes it impossible to determine the best approaches on projects undergoing CIA.

We have come to learn that CIA is one piece of a puzzle within EIA, whereby EIA is facilitating an entry point to addressing climate issues, which has been recognised in the literature (Jirricka-Purrer et al (2018), Hellsten et al (2022)) and in the interviews. Therefore, CIA should not be considered against a stagnant timeline or without the wider context and interactions extending beyond the EIA itself. This means considering the before, during and after the EIA process including early-stage project input and follow-up and monitoring during construction and operation. It also means we need to stop siloing disciplines across the EIA and outside of it including academia, construction, industry, government. The aim needs to be consolidating bottom-up and top-down climate measures with guidance that is aligned across disciplines.

Guidance

The misinterpretation of guidance was highlighted in the interviews. From reviewing the guidance documents, it is evident that providing enough detail and using a methodical approach is likely to reduce this tendency but may only be feasible for sector specific guidance rather than overarching documents which may be too high-level. Despite the recognition in the literature and the recently updated IEMA guidance attempting to provide further clarity on significance ratings and

contextualising impacts, it became clear that there is still ambiguity in this regard, which is also reflected in the uncertainty surrounding cumulative impacts. It is generally accepted that again policy should be used to contextualise the impacts to make them relevant for EIA procedures – contributing to significance ratings and cumulative impacts. However, the successful integration of policy to CIA and with other environmental and sustainability tools on the ground has not happened to date.

When looking beyond compliance at policies and procedures associated with CIA, a practitioner should not be solely focused on meeting minimum legislative requirements but maintain perspective on the big picture and push for transformative solutions to drive climate action on projects.

Data and Implementation

Mitigation and Adaptation Solutions

These criteria (‘mitigation and adaptation’ and ‘design enhancements’) comprised some of the worst performing against the framework, which is quite concerning given that one of the key purposes of the EIA process is to instigate an iterative feedback loop to the design team that acts to reduce negative impacts, as discussed in the interviews. It appears that the guidance documents and the best practice CIA procedures to date have been focused on measuring and justifying the impacts rather than reducing impacts or improving the project outcomes. The importance of design enhancement through CIA has also not been explored in the literature to date.

The interviews revealed that developers do not view CIA as the most useful means for driving action because they feel it is separated from what happens on the ground, which is likely true. This is despite the widely held belief that driving action from the early stages of a project is crucial for climate action in the built environment. As such, it is paramount that CIA procedures are integrated with construction practices and implementation solutions (including other sustainability tools) whilst ensuring that the benefits and possibilities of properly leveraging the CIA process are understood by all. To facilitate this, the provision of practical advice, including tangible and actionable measures, should be prioritised within the guidance documents, particularly relating to stakeholder engagement, collaboration, decision making, and the development of design solutions whereby it is currently lacking (according to the interviews and assessment results).

Some guidance documents provide high-level guidelines relating to these issues, for example the PAS2080 standard provides information around decision making and the IEMA guidance recognises the importance of stakeholder engagement for design. However, there is a failure to frame the information in a way that is directly actionable for a CIA practitioner or design team. It should be noted that several documents attempted to cover this off by including details regarding project team ‘roles’ – though the assigning of roles was not mentioned once in the interviews (indicating it may not be the most relevant).

It is recognised that solutions cannot always be prescriptive when developing practical guidance for mitigation and adaptation, as it depends on the design, carbon ‘hotspots,’ and the vulnerability to a changing climate. However, we need to incorporate consolidated evidence and understand the ‘how’ in terms of embedding mitigation so that potential approaches can be recommended within the guidance documents, at least as a starting point, to facilitate real action on the ground. Furthermore, the issues and constraints felt by the construction sector need to be considered to ensure any guidance given to practitioners is aligned to the needs of the contractor. This was highlighted throughout the interview responses, whereby it is the consensus amongst practitioners that contractors as well as various other disciplines need to be engaged to develop and embed mitigation and adaptation solutions, taking a whole-systems approach.

It is also evident that there has been a much greater focus on mitigation than adaptation to date, likely due to the weaker policy drivers and more difficult target setting (as solutions need to be informed by changing climate) as highlighted in the interviews. Several interviewees also depicted that people are not worried about climate change effects in Ireland which may contribute to the lesser focus on adaptation.

Data Availability and Overcoming Uncertainty

It was brought to light in the interviews that data can be the determining factor in deciding if the CIA will be able to inform climate action on projects, particularly in terms of ‘measuring innovation’ and determining how a mitigation or adaptation solution will perform to reduce a negative impact. It is also well understood that the detail is frequently lacking at the early stages of the project which can make it difficult to obtain data, in addition to the added uncertainty from future climate change projections. The lack of tangible actions for practitioners within the guidance documents is inter-connected with the lack of guidance related to data collection and interpretation.

It was also highlighted in the interviews that the data collection process is typically started too late in the project or EIA timeline to allow for the time to attempt to fill any data gaps.

It should be noted that there were some data sources provided within the guidance documents which were helpful, however, more detailed information on benchmarking, assumptions, and methodologies for overcoming data uncertainties was entirely lacking. The data sources were more typically focused on GHG assessment and mitigation rather than adaptation. This is connected to the poor performance on solutions development whereby one will not successfully develop or implement solutions without the data to back them up and justify their use.

In addition, the well-recognised lack of monitoring and follow-up in CIA and EIA, documented in literature (Nisbet et al, 2022) also contributes to the potential data gaps, as the impacts of implemented solutions are not being measured and recorded for future benchmarks. This type of follow-up and record keeping would allow for adaptive management referenced in the literature by Hochstrasser (2013), which is in other words ‘learning by doing’ (and should also be a collaborative, multidisciplinary endeavor).

Furthermore, partnering with academia and industry to undertake research and pilot projects to test novel technologies and gather data on their performance (for example, using EPDs) is crucial to seeing change in this regard. This would help with enabling the inclusion of sample mitigation and adaptation solutions (including examples and tangible actions) in the guidance with tried and tested methods that practitioners can incorporate and justify to developers. There is a need to continue research (and in communication with industry) in several areas in addition to testing new technologies for practical application. For example, collecting evidence on climate projections and to determine how best to use climate data for a changing future baseline (fundamental to the ‘do-something’ versus ‘do-nothing’ scenarios for CIA), was discussed throughout the interviews. If the guidance cannot give the starting point in terms of the ‘how’ for climate action than we cannot expect project teams to do so.

Construction Sector

When discussing the opportunities and challenges all the developers had a lot to say on sustainability ratings² for new developments which was not as much of a focus for other

² Sustainability ratings include building and infrastructure certification processes to measure a projects contribution to environmental and social sustainability metrics including (but not limited too) BREEAM, LEED, HPI, CEEQUAL, and WELL.

interviewees. This is likely due to the shift in focus from planning stage to implementation stage. The implementation stage is crucial for developers and is more representative of what happens on the ground. The developers all agreed these ratings were deemed more practical on the ground than CIA as the building is physically checked which does not happen with EIA / CIA (reflective of the lack of follow up (Nisbet et al, 2022)) and have tangible actions built in such as requirements for contractors.

It is crucial that the construction sector is better considered throughout the CIA process. The findings of this research have shown that the construction sector is given little attention in policy and in the guidance documents though in practice, there is a significant reliance on the contractor to make things happen, evidenced by the interviews. It was recommended in the interviews that construction contracts are utilised to obligate the contractor to incorporate mitigation and adaptation solutions, however, it should be noted that it is already a legal imperative to incorporate mitigation contained within an EIAR dependent on the planning conditions. Furthermore, if the contractor is not happy to include measures within an EIAR they certainly will not be happy to include it in a contract without any other changes to the premise. As documented by Hurlimann et al (2022), there needs to be better supports for the construction sector including training, funding, research, and knowledge sharing which has been supported by the findings of this research. The literature recommends that the construction sector is engaged early to inform project teams of the problems that are constraining the implementation of mitigation and adaptation on projects so that the best support can be determined (Attia, 2018).

Monitoring

The importance of monitoring and follow-up on post-CIA data collection for the benefit of adaptive management and ongoing learning has been previously mentioned. The findings of this research suggest that monitoring and follow-up is not a focus point for most practitioners in practice and is also a significant weak area in the guidance documents, with no applications of CIA monitoring found throughout this research. This is despite being recognised in the literature as bringing substantial benefits to the overall EIA process and some practitioners recognising its importance (Nisbet et al, 2022). This needs to change if adaptive management is going to be leveraged and the issues around data uncertainty are going to be improved.

Taking the 'beyond compliance' perspective when considering data and implementation for CIA, should mean the practitioner will not only focus on justifying the impacts but will realise their role in pushing to reduce climate impacts with new solutions whilst monitoring their success for adaptive learning.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Engagement and Collaboration

Considering appropriately integrating climate change into EIA has led us to realise that climate needs to be treated differently to other environmental receptors which has also highlighted some weakness associated with the EIA process itself. Although climate needs to be considered differently to other environmental receptors, we also need to fully understand how climate interacts with those other receptors, as well disciplines outside of the EIA process. Furthermore, the expectation around inter-relationships across the EIA needs to move away from the compliance tick-box ‘wishy washy’ approach applied to date (as described in the interviews). This approach is likely driven by the EPA EIA guidance (EPA, 2022) which suggests a literal tick-box approach to measuring inter-relationships. Whilst a type of methodical approach to assessing the inter-relationships may have a place, the inter-relationships need to be considered by taking a holistic (or ‘whole-systems’) approach from the outset of the project regardless, discussed throughout the interviews. This holistic approach needs to be maintained throughout the CIA process, continuing the extensive stakeholder engagement and collaboration. This type of holistic approach can be more easily applied when we ‘zoom out’ and apply more strategic thinking than might be common practice at project level, before zooming in to the project specifics.

The interdisciplinary engagement and collaboration between disciplines is another underperforming criterion against the framework and an evident gap in current CIA practices and guidance documents. This gap further demonstrates the unbalanced focus on assessment compliance rather than taking a holistic approach that is connected to transformational, sustainable development. The results of the assessment framework showed that the guidance documents did not adequately cover the interactions between climate risk and emissions reductions, let alone any other ‘non-climate’ disciplines. However, as previously mentioned, the EU Climate and Biodiversity EIA guidance document, though outdated, manages to introduce important concepts related to interdisciplinary engagement, collaborative approaches and communicating uncertainty. This guidance (or similar) should be updated, and these concepts built upon to include more tangible methodical approaches that practitioners can apply directly in practice.

Stakeholder Process

It was pointed out in the interviews that typically the CIA is delivered as quickly as possible due to time constraints placed on the EIA, usually when the design is already well-developed. This is

due to developers seeing EIA as an inconvenient hurdle rather than an opportunity, which reflects the interview findings. This means that incorporating extensive stakeholder engagement or creating opportunities for collaborative design enhancement is extremely challenging. To overcome this gap, a shift in the EIA process itself needs to happen to facilitate this necessary collaboration. Furthermore, it is likely that if interdisciplinary engagement is improved throughout the CIA process, many of the other issues would also improve, from both an assessment and solutions stand-point. This is in line with the findings from literature including the Innes (1998) approach to communicative planning and the Doelle and Majekolagbe (2023) recommendation for meaningful engagement for climate integration to EIA.

The careful communication and framing needed when undertaking stakeholder engagement to encourage buy-in and ensure successful collaboration was highlighted in the interviews. Specifically, the need to create ‘win-win’ situations, understand motivations, and demonstrate the benefits in a meaningful way, whilst still ensuring that uncertainties and challenges are communicated. In this way CIA can be used as an educational tool, however, to achieve this, there needs to be guidance for practitioners to help them change current methods and make improvements especially given the typical EIA constraints.

Looking beyond compliance when considering interdisciplinary collaboration for CIA will result in practitioners being more inclined to take a whole-systems approach to assessment and implementation of mitigation and adaptation solutions, seeking input from a wide range of disciplines early and throughout the process.

Recommendations

This research presents several new insights on CIA procedures, as discussed in the previous section, which have been translated into summarised recommendations not only for CIA practitioners but for different societal actors that play a role in the success of CIA (including policy makers, standards bodies, construction workers, designers, academics, and researchers).

The research has been focused on Ireland, but these insights and recommendations can also be applicable to other countries in Europe and potentially other regions. Whilst EIA is acknowledged as the entry point for climate action, these recommendations may also be applied to other projects and contexts outside of EIA and planning. Ultimately, the transformational changes required to

deliver climate action in the built environment will require a level of development which must be conducted without derailing climate objectives.

The recommendations draw upon the three thematic groupings of consolidated insights, outlined in the previous section (see **Figure 4**) though noting there is inherent overlap between the three themes. This section aims to portray actionable solutions for each theme, first discussed in more general terms, followed by a summary of condensed actions.

Policy and Procedures

Policy makers and governments have a responsibility to consider a longer-term vision when setting policies including providing direction in terms of planning and development of the built environment and how it fits with a climate future. This vision must shed light on how these objectives will be delivered in the long term with consideration for practical implementation and feasibility including, for example, materials, risks, supply chains and resources (Attia, 2018). These practical considerations need to be synergistic with the policy vision instead of an afterthought. The various stakeholders who will be directly responsible for delivering these targets on the ground, in particular the construction sector, must be extensively consulted in developing future policy targets.

It is widely acknowledged that governments tend to prefer a narrow vision, shorter-term policy lens (Zhou et al, 2022). Furthermore, it was recognised in the interviews that certain policy mechanisms like 5-year carbon budgets have a much shorter lifespan than infrastructure being developed today. Conflicting policies have also been identified as a barrier to understanding the necessary objectives for projects, with practitioners highlighting in the interviews that projects need to align to government targets. The vision set by policy makers must, therefore, consolidate bottom-up and top-down approaches, consider the longer-term vision to 2050 and beyond and be consistent across the policy landscape.

CIA practitioners need to ensure that any policies or similar contextualising information being used to justify a climate impact in EIA is balanced. For example, by avoiding the over-reliance on a comparison against a short-term carbon budget but also comparing to longer term projections (for both climate risk and GHG emissions). We are ultimately aiming for a 'Net Zero' by 2050 future (in accordance with the legally binding Climate Act), and as highlighted by practitioners in this research, developments built now are not coming close to achieving Net Zero despite being

operational in 2050 (UNEP, 2022). This long-term policy vision also needs to demonstrate the benefit of making smaller but important changes now which will add up over time to realise a bigger goal.

Such recommendations would help to improve the following in CIA procedures and associated guidance (based on the criteria from the assessment framework): (1) Policy integration, (2) significance ratings, (3) design enhancement, and (4) cumulative impact assessment.

Data and Implementation

It is widely recognised by literature, and confirmed by this research, that global climate change can feel intangible for projects due to the lack of clarity on scaling climate policy objectives to ground level. Therefore, it would be beneficial to address this by providing guidance on the scaling pathway from policy to project level, showing the targets and recommended actions along the scale. For example, the interviews highlighted the use of corporate strategies and city-scale climate action plans as being potential intermediaries between high-level policy and ground level action. The use of this type of intentional hierarchy (for example, Roy (2022)) could facilitate a methodical approach to setting this pathway and providing tangible actions for practitioners and developers by using the combined landscape of documents.

Such a hierarchy could be used in CIA guidance documents to encompass the top-down overarching guidelines (Attia, 2018) to bottom-up detailed design standards (Priore et al, 2022) and demonstrate the interactions with policies, other standards, and sustainability tools. The hierarchy should regard the expected contents and policy integration across each level and be developed with input from a wide variety of disciplines. This could be similar to the Mayembe et al (2023) approach to climate integration levels but across the system of guidance documents instead of within the EIA. The guidance documents must clearly reference and link to other documents and tools (for example, the TII CIA standards reference, complement, and utilise concepts from other guidance documents).

Similarly, policy makers need to consider how top-down climate policies are distributed at ground level implementation and provide appropriate direction on scaling down the requirements (OECD, 2013). This may also include expectations in terms of a policy hierarchy (which could be complementary to a hierarchy of guidance for practitioners). Furthermore, policy makers need to consider the negative consequence of legislative requirements leading to a ‘compliance game’ and

ensure that the drive for sustainable development is maintained. This can be done by aptly integrating the big picture into the more granular objectives.

These top-down policies and resulting guidance must include the incorporation of bottom-up insights (for example planning, funding, resources, materials, uncertainty, risks, and conflicting targets). This should be facilitated by undertaking extensive research focused on practical application of climate solutions, in addition to stakeholder engagement, particularly with the construction sector, and in partnership with academia. This research should focus on gathering data related to the implementation stage of mitigation and adaptation including performance measurement, and monitoring which will contribute to overcoming uncertainty. The research studies should be designed with contractors, developers, and other stakeholders to ensure barriers to implementation are addressed.

Such recommendations would help to improve the following in CIA procedures and associated guidance (based on the criteria from the assessment framework): (1) Policy integration, (2) mitigation and adaptation solutions, and (3) design enhancement.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration

CIA practitioners need to ensure their project teams and developers recognise the potential for EIA as an entry point to climate action in the built environment, fully realising the benefits and opportunities. Practitioners and their teams need to start as early as possible in the project, collecting data and developing a plan for the CIA including measuring the impacts, mitigation and adaptation solutions, follow-up, and monitoring.

There needs to be a cultural shift in how we approach CIA (and EIA), to move away from these siloed efforts to take a holistic approach that harnesses interdisciplinarity and drives transformation through development. A combined effort from academia and industry is needed to increase research, gather data, evidence, and best practice advice regarding new mitigation and adaptation solutions and novel technologies that can be incorporated into the guidance documents. The follow-up after the EIA needs to incorporate guidance on monitoring and data collection / interpretation to facilitate ongoing learning (which could be in partnerships with government and academia) to help with overcoming uncertainties and supporting innovation and measuring the outcomes to use for future projects. The communication of such efforts must be amplified to ensure a shared understanding across industry.

Practitioners need to collaborate extensively from the earliest stages possible to improve the design to reduce climate impacts, realising the time and resources required to do so, and get the most out of the CIA process. This collaboration must include engagement across EIA disciplines but also extend to disciplines outside of the EIA. Furthermore, practical advice on stakeholder engagement and collaboration including approaches to workshopping, interviews, information gathering, and interpretation need to be prioritised in the guidance.

Such recommendations would help to improve the following in CIA procedures and associated guidance (based on the criteria from the assessment framework): (1) Effectiveness of the guidance that is in place, (2) inter-relationships across disciplines, (3) baselines development, (4) early-stage input to projects, and (5) design enhancement.

Summary of Key Recommendations

The key learnings and recommendations are summarised below, in accordance with the thematic groupings identified upon consolidating the research insights (see **Figure 4**).

1. Policies and Procedures

1.1. The **construction sector** needs to be better considered in the development of policy. The sector needs more **specific guidance** in relation to the implementation of policy targets on the ground, whereby, the construction sector is a fundamental sector in enabling the achievement of targets through the required development. This needs to include consideration for materials, risks, supply chains, and resources.

1.2. Policy makers need to be proactive about getting **bottom-up input** from the construction sector and other disciplines to set guidelines for **ground level action whilst maintaining a long-term vision**. For example, guidance on developing project level carbon budgets for different sectors or considering carbon budgets in development plans would be extremely effective at guiding the achievement of targets. The CIA guidance documents need to include instructions on contextualising impacts against **longer term projections** and contribution to achieving a **Net Zero by 2050** future.

1.3. The standard bodies need to ensure that different guidelines, standards, and tools work together to achieve better outcomes rather than working in isolation and resulting in nearly competing efforts. There needs to be **open dialogue** between the different standards bodies as well as the users of these other resources to facilitate this.

2. Data and Implementation

2.1. There needs to be a **consolidation of the guidance and tools** for dealing with climate impacts in construction and development sector. It needs to be possible to see how various guidance documents interact with others and how these come together. Ideally, this would be **mapped out** with a **tiered hierarchy structure** that moves from top down to bottom up, with guidance on the scaling pathway which could be aligned to policy.

2.2. More guidance on **mitigation and adaptation solutions** is needed, including **data** on the climate benefits, whereby, practitioners need to ensure negative impacts can be reduced, not just measured. There is opportunity for partnership between academia, government, and industry to push for **research** solutions that include pilot projects and means for data collection and **performance monitoring**.

3. Interdisciplinary Collaboration

3.1. The **construction sector** needs to contribute to the design of research studies, so that the challenges with implementing solutions can be overcome. Standards bodies need to focus on creating **partnerships** across disciplines to continue to build data and develop guidelines on implementing new solutions.

3.2. There needs to be a **cultural shift** around CIA and EIA procedures, to look beyond compliance and maximise the opportunity to use CIA to implement top-down policies at ground level. This need to move away from a purely compliance focused mindset is also relevant to contexts outside of EIA. This cultural shift can be facilitated by **training** and a **change in dialogue** surrounding EIA / CIA. The CIA practitioner needs to influence the team from beginning and get the developer on board with the process.

3.3. There needs to be more **guidance on stakeholder engagement** which facilitates a collaborative framing from the outset of the project whereby looking beyond compliance implements a **holistic effort** rather than isolating CIA from other disciplines. The guidance documents need to be updated to include this new approach, with input from a wider variety of stakeholders in the development of the guidance.

Conclusion

This research has successfully demonstrated the weaknesses associated with the current best practice approaches to CIA for the built environment in Ireland's planning and development context. The different research components including the literature review, interviews and assessment of guidance documents were consolidated to provide cross-cutting insights. The findings could be categorised into three inter-related themes ((1) policies and procedures, (2) data and implementation, and (3) interdisciplinary collaboration). To understand the intersection between these themes and make improvements to CIA practices, it is essential to look at the bigger picture and not focus solely on legislative compliance, in other words look 'beyond-compliance.'

The findings from the literature review provided insight into regulatory expectations and potential approaches for integrating climate into EIA procedures, giving an indication of high-level procedural challenges. The interviews with practitioners provided more detailed perspective on a variety of opportunities and challenges associated with EIA, revealing broad insights focused on the practical application of CIA. The assessment of guidance documents showed the areas in which current best practices are performing well and where there are weaknesses which correlated with the challenges discussed by practitioners. The findings show that while guidance documents have the potential to be the lever that connects climate policy targets and project level action, there are several challenges that need to be overcome to successfully leverage this potential.

EIA provides a fantastic entry point for climate action which can be used to obligate change, that we must certainly maximise, but will only be possible if developers and project teams understand the potential opportunities of a well-delivered CIA. Furthermore, there needs to be changes outside of EIA, by other societal actors including policy makers, designers, construction workers, and researchers, to facilitate better outcomes for CIA. Climate is an environmental receptor which requires us to rethink our approach to EIA and thus this research has served to highlight the much needed cultural shift in planning and development. We must stop approaching CIA and EIA solely from a regulatory compliance exercise and use it as a tool for driving transformational change through sustainable development.

When looking beyond compliance a practitioner will not be solely focused on meeting minimum legislative requirements. They will ensure that they not only justify climate impacts but will try to drive them down. They will realise their role in collaborating with a wide range of disciplines to improve their assessment and push for transformative solutions for mitigation and adaptation on projects.

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Appendix A: Interview Questionnaire

1. What is your understanding of CIA?
2. Do you think that climate mitigation and climate adaptation is being successfully implemented on new projects in the built environment to date?
3. Do you think that CIA can make a difference in terms of climate action for projects in the built environment?
4. What are the main challenges being faced by practitioners when undertaking CIA? Pick 2 from the below list or suggest an alternative:
 - Baselines
 - Climate action in design
 - Significance ratings
 - Inter-relationships
 - Mitigation
 - Cumulative impacts
5. When carrying out EIA / CIA is it possible to integrate climate policy targets?
6. Do you think current CIA procedures can be improved?
7. What do you think are the greatest opportunities with implementing climate action through EIA / CIA procedures? Pick 2 from the below list or suggest an alternative:
 - Mitigation
 - Alignment with policy
 - Design enhancements
 - Scope for influence
 - Improvements across the EIA
 - Motivation for developers
8. Is there anything you would like to find out from this research that would help you on projects?